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Preface

Negative emission solutions are expected to play a pivotal role in future climate actions and net-zero emissions policy scenarios. To date, most climate actions have focused on phasing out fossil fuels and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in, for example, industry, electricity, and transport. While zero-emission trajectories in these sectors will remain a priority for decades to come, it is expected that residual GHG emissions will remain. To be able to fulfil the Paris Agreement and meet the world's climate goals research, policy and markets are increasingly looking at negative emission solutions.

Therefore, the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work together in order to:

- Estimate the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assess the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Map their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

LANDMARC is an interdisciplinary consortium with expertise in ecology, engineering, climate sciences, global carbon cycle, soil sciences, satellite earth observation sciences, agronomy, economics, social sciences, and business. There is a balanced representation of partners from academia, SMEs, and NGOs from the EU, Africa, Asia and the Americas, which ensures wide coverage of LMTs operating in different contexts (e.g., climates, land-use practices, socio-economic etc.) and spatial scales.

The LANDMARC project consortium:

This deliverable aims to combine different ideas in the same concept, and this concept can be translated into a practical application. It starts with an idea inspired by a case study, following a working trip of the Landmarc team to Colombia in October 2022, where several facilities were visited, and meetings were held

with multiple stakeholders of palm oil cultivation. The palm oil sector opened to the Landmarc Project, and it was possible to become aware of the significant progress that this important Colombian production sector is making to reconcile productivity, sustainability, biodiversity maintenance and mitigation. This compatibility is made possible by the application of advanced economic concepts, in which the different elements of the crop value chain relate to each other, forming a hub of social, economic, ecological and climatic interests that collaborate with each other in a natural way.

With this source of inspiration, the Landmarc team sought a new perspective, studying the different case studies and the parallels between them, and looking at how the concept of economic relations in the Colombian palm oil sector could be the basis for new approaches that integrate economic relations within a circular economy diagram. In this way, the concept was first developed, and then the practical application to the different case studies presented below was sought.

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Without the selfless work, quality of information, knowledge, and experience that they bring to the LANDMARC team, the document presented here could not have moved from a general conceptual approach to one more focused on concrete land use practices at county scales.

Practice and experience from the world of agriculture and forestry, technology transfer, economic and social sciences and engineering work hand in hand and form the basis of this deliverable. Farmers, foresters, and other stakeholders in land use management working in rural areas have knowledge to share in the field of mitigation. It is the duty of science to take them into account so that this know-how reaches decision-makers and policies are oriented towards the common good that the rural world represents.

Finally, special mention is made of the palm oil sector and institutions, Cenipalma and Fedepalma in Colombia, with the support of Dr. Edwin Cristancho-Pinilla, who organised a workshop inviting part of the LANDMARC team in October 2022 on a one week field visit. This field visit was instrumental to learning about different best sustainable land management practices, and whose good agricultural, environmental, adaptation and mitigation practices, as well as social and economic integration with rural Colombian communities, have been the seed that has inspired the development of this document.

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Executive summary

In response to the current climate crisis and since the Paris Agreement (COP21), there has been widespread international agreement on limiting global warming to below 2°C. Two recent IPCC reports have emphasised that the most feasible pathway to limiting warming to 2°C or less is to deploy both climate mitigation (emissions reduction) and intervention (carbon dioxide removal) to achieve “net negative emissions” by the end of this century. In addition, the IPCC 5th Assessment Report affirms that land can sequester more than a third of our carbon dioxide emissions, and many countries already consider land-based mitigation measures in their Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), though relatively few have specific targets or realistic strategies for scaling up. Aside from the importance of the land use sector for successful climate change mitigation, developments in the sector are also closely tied to the achievement of many Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in particular SDG2 Zero Hunger, SDG6 Clean Water and Sanitation, SDG12 Responsible Consumption and Production, and SDG15 Life on Land.

This report is part of the LANDMARC project and aims to provide a new conceptual approach that places Land-use Based Mitigation Technologies and Practices (LMTs) in agriculture, forestry and other land use (AFOLU) sectors as a driver of new social and economic developments in the rural environment. This approach is capable of being the axis on which a productive fabric based on circular economy criteria pivots, in which relationships are established between the different agents in the territory. LMTs can combine innovation with tradition, productivity with sustainability, and science with empirical technique. This approach positions LMTs as an axis on which a productive fabric based on circular economy criteria pivots, and as a place where relationships can be established between the different agents in the rural territory.

This document explores the synergies and opportunities that open up when responding to social and climate challenges. It begins by explaining the conceptual approach we use, and then moves on to show how, in practice, that approach could be potentially applied to develop a circular economy in a rural context or with low population located outside of main cities and towns. The rural environment is facing a serious economic, environmental, and demographic crisis. But it can also offer real responses to the climate, social and economic challenges that the urban and industrial environment is bringing to the table for 21st century societies. These responses to the urban world can be directed so that they are also solutions to the problems of the rural environment. This requires designs that consider medium and long-term socio-economic approaches, established on a solid and well-structured spatial planning basis.

The content provided in this deliverable draws inspiration from the valuable contributions made by the LANDMARC team since the start of the project in July 2020. It is built on a foundation of observation and collection of empirical knowledge in case studies, and is built on socio-economic relationships around land-based mitigation technologies. The conceptual diagram is derived from the arrangement of different variables, classified into categories that connect sociology, economics, and environmental sciences in the rural environment.

Abbreviations and definitions

LMT	Land-use based Mitigation Technologies
AFOLU	Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use
HNV	High Nature Value
BECCS	BioEnergy with Carbon Capture and Storage
CMMT	Carbon Measurement and Monitoring Tool
CS	Case Study
EO	Earth Observation
GPP	Gross Primary Production
NEP	Net Ecosystem Production
NPP	Net Primary Production
RS	Remote Sensing

1. Introduction

LANDMARC aims at helping land-managers to use the territory in sustainable ways that are beneficial not only from a climate perspective, but also for the rural communities -including areas with low population located outside of main cities and towns- that live and work on that territory. Land-managers can include farmers, forest managers, and other land right holders). The LMTs (land-based mitigation technologies and practices) studied in LANDMARC are carefully chosen to deliver additional benefits together with their potential for carbon sequestration. LMTs are defined as land-based technologies *and* practices that consider *mitigation* and *carbon sink potential* along with co-benefit for social and environmental sustainability in the agriculture, forestry and other land use (AFOLU) sectors. These benefits include, but are not limited to, improving biodiversity and providing opportunities for new sustainable business models that can alleviate the ever-increasing climate risks that rural communities are facing.

This can only be done by coupling LANDMARC's diverse team of researchers with local land-users, who hold their region's history, and understand what land-use practices work and do not work in that context. That is why LANDMARC's consortium brings together a wide range of social scientists, experts in Earth observation technology, and computer modellers, to generate research that can work as a helpful decision-making toolkit for agribusinesses and other land-users.

1.1 Who this guide is for

The objective of this best management practices guide is to provide land use managers who wish to practically apply LMTs a basic framework to create a business model around the LMT considering the environmental, societal, and economic needs of the area. Best practices in land use practices are presented here in a circular economy diagram that integrates mitigation, land management, innovation, technology, entrepreneurship, employment, population fixation and attraction of youth and female talent to rural areas. This way, LMTs are applied for climate mitigation purposes as well as to promote other economic, social, and environmental goals, harnessing their full potential.

1.2. How to read this guide

This guide begins with a review of the importance of LMTs as a regional economic opportunity (section 2). This review then provides a background to introducing the best management practice. The guide is structured around the concept of the *LMT Hub scheme*, which is introduced theoretically in section 3 as an overall best practice. . Sections 4 to 6 then focus on the application of LMT in different geographical contexts. LMTs are not only highly individual and context dependent, but also depend on unique networks of stakeholders and land use managers regionally and around the world; but these diverse LMTs can all be adapted to the overarching LMT Hub scheme to develop business models. However, due to the already mentioned individuality of each particular region and LMT, the final outputs will vary greatly in character and depth of development. That is why this best management practices guide provides 11 case studies as examples, arranged by LMT type in sections 4-6 (table 1).

Table 1. Case studies, case study countries and LMTs presented in this guide as business models

LMT type	Case study country	Case study LMT
Forest management and agroforestry	Spain	Afforestation of degraded agricultural land, adaptation, mitigation, and circular economy
	Portugal and Spain	Montados and dehesas. Adaptation, mitigation, and circular economy
	Kenya	Integrated soil fertility management combined with agroforestry and animal husbandry
	Germany	Forest management
	Burkina Faso	Agroforestry and cropland management
Agriculture	Nepal	Improving rice production
	Canada	Land restoration and food production
	The Netherlands	Sustainable agriculture
Biogas	Indonesia	Biogas implementation for agroforestry farmers
	Sweden	Emission avoidance combining BECCS and biochar
	Ukraine	A sustainable biogas energy system and organic agriculture

These LMT types are categorised into three sectors: forest management and agroforestry; agriculture; and biogas. Some case studies, however, combine elements of two of these categories, such as agriculture and biogas. These have been included in the section that was considered dominant within the LMT application. Finally, section 7 includes a series of concluding remarks and outlines future directions for research and application.

2. Land mitigation technologies as a regional economic opportunity

The rural environment is facing a socio-economic crisis. This is directly related to the loss of population, which for various reasons, has been on a progressive downward trend in recent decades, with migratory movements mainly from rural to urban areas¹. This loss of population also relates to one of the main causes of the decline of natural and agricultural ecosystems – the abandonment of towns and cities². Towns and cities in rural areas are home to inhabitants traditionally dedicated to agriculture or forestry, so the abandonment of those towns and cities has consequences for the degradation of agricultural land use.

Together with the abandonment of the rural population, traditional agricultural, livestock, and forestry land uses are facing other complex social and environmental challenges. These include climate change and biodiversity loss, to name but a few, which are manifested in a particular way in each geographical region. For instance, in regions with a Mediterranean climate, the main risks to the land are drought, desertification, and an increase in forest fires. On the other hand, in Central and Northern Europe, the major climate-related disturbances arise from changes in extreme weather events such as heatwaves, cold waves, and recurring floods, which result in significant losses and material damage (see D4.2 “Climatic risk assessment and initial risk management plan” for more details on climatic risks for LMTs in different geographical regions).

This deliverable explores new opportunities for agriculture and forestry, the traditional livelihoods of Europe's rural populations, in the face of the challenges of depopulation and climate change. These opportunities come from the fact that good practices in forestry and agriculture offer society a sink for carbon and other greenhouse gases (GHG). This creates an opportunity to mitigate climate change, and can be a driving force for attracting new business models to Europe's rural areas. Such business models would be based on the one hand, on traditional economic pillars, and on the other hand, on technologies and applied innovation. These models can potentially attract a young and/or diverse talent pool to the rural environment, generating new jobs and reducing population loss, taking advantage of the added value of agro-ecosystems for mitigation.

2.1. A circular economy for rural areas

Land management and include both traditional and newer integrated ways of land management. Traditional ways of using land include intensive agriculture, extensive livestock farming, and forest management (where humans intervene to manage the forest growth). More recent integrated methods can combine different mitigation and adaptation technologies and practices together -like the use of sustainable biomass for energy generation- which have the potential to make a positive impact on the socio-economic and environmental challenges of depopulation and climate change mentioned above. Because good management practices applied to these land uses, and adjusted to the particular rural environment, can make it easier to adapt to the impacts of climate change (like drought for example) or to

¹ https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/ministerio/servicios/analisis-y-prospectiva/ayp_demografiaenlapoblacionrural2020_tcm30-583987.pdf

² https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/biodiversidad/temas/desertificacion-restauracion/lucha-contra-la-desertificacion/lch_espana.aspx

mitigate its effects; for instance by reducing the impact of hydrological floods or carbon sinks, to cite two cases³.

There are possibilities of integrating these good land use management practices into a circular economy system, creating new market value chains by bringing together the needed resources, skills, technologies and capacities. For instance, these agro-ecosystem services addressing both adaptation and mitigation challenges are an economic and social opportunity for the rural environment and for the people who live in it or may live there. For this reason, young people and women are population segments that can contribute to or lead in these business models and contribute to developing the social and economic fabric of a new rural economy based on the LMT hub concept.

The goal is to present an LMT hub concept based on a circular economy model centred around land management in rural areas by initially conceptualising the hub and to begin implementing the concept or provide the knowledge for stakeholders in case studies to implement it within and beyond the LANDMARC project. This model provides a range of possibilities for rural areas and enhances their prospects for both employment and wealth generation. It does this by leveraging the significant economic, social and environmental value that each element of the hub contributes to society.

The underlying principle of the LMT hub concept is effective land use management and the adoption of sound agricultural and forestry practices can create significant value by generating agro-ecosystem services. These services can be monetized, attracting skilled individuals and stimulating employment and new business opportunities in rural regions as well as contributing to overall environmental sustainability.

Within a circular economy framework, a value chain is established through the use of land mitigation technologies (LMTs) which encompasses activities ranging from plant cultivation in nurseries and applied research to carbon sequestration monitoring and soil regeneration, involving multiple market players.

2.2. A two-way knowledge transfer

Sometimes these new technologies and practices are a return to traditional and more orderly land use management. Other times, sustainable management trends are advancing, and new concepts are being integrated. A new approach to land management will need to consider multiple benefits for sustainability, soil conservation, biodiversity preservation, increasing resilience to extreme events as well as climate change mitigation potential from different approaches, such as carbon and other GHG sequestration and storage.

Best soil management practices require the transfer of knowledge and know-how from science and technology to farmers, livestock breeders and foresters. But this transfer must go in both directions. It is crucial for science and technology to gather the knowledge and experience of the people who are, and work, on the ground, and know better than experts the real (and urgent) issues and challenges they face every day in land management. Transfer of knowledge and learning is therefore an essential aspect of the

³ https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/biodiversidad/temas/desertificacion-restauracion/lucha-contra-la-desertificacion/lch_pand_diagnostico_espana.aspx

LMT hub. As an example of great progress in terms of knowledge transfer, the EIP AGRI, through its different operational groups, has been working in Europe for some years⁴ with great success⁵.

Some of the practices of sustainable approaches to land use management in rural areas include: techniques for conserving or regenerating soil, efficient water management in irrigation systems, orderly forest management to prevent fires, optimising nutrient usage, employing organic fertilisation, utilising native plants adapted for planting, and employing direct sowing techniques. In addition, the rural environment provides products and services to the urban population and industrial sectors, which need to be appropriately quantified and monetized.

The adoption of improved land use management practices is particularly relevant for regions where a specific land use dominates or has a strong presence, and where a sustainable transition towards better practices serves as the pivot point for driving progress.

2.3. How measuring tools can turn carbon credits into a real opportunity for land-managers

By focusing on the concept of implementing LMTs, technologies and land-use practices that effectively mitigate climate change, a new socio-economic territorial framework can be established. This framework serves as the core of a circular economy model within a specific rural region, with a scale determined by the land itself.

LMTs can add value to the ecosystem services and provide a necessity for new business models to be economically viable and to thrive under the circular economy diagram. But this added value must also be translatable into monetary values. And these values must in turn be credible and be able to offer certainty in the markets. Measurement of these values, then, requires accuracy, reliability, credibility, verifiability and adequate area size to make monitoring feasible.

With these elements in place, carbon markets and carbon credits offer a real opportunity to develop new business models. This is because they can translate the value of carbon sequestration and storage into units that, once measured, have a tangible economic value in the market.

In this sense, the carbon measurement tools that are being tested in the different LANDMARC case studies, and the combination of these techniques (see Deliverables 3.3 and 3.8) are examples of practical technological applications of carbon measurement in real mitigation case studies based on land use. The tools can work separately or in synergy with each other, forming complex and complementary methodologies, to provide greater precision and scaling of values, reducing implementation costs and convincing investors of the market potential and cost effectiveness of the LMT solutions.

In this case, we are dealing with an element of the value chain that can offer diverse possibilities and variants when it comes to generating new niches of entrepreneurship, work and, therefore, population settlement. Applied digitalisation arises to respond to the demand for services that the rural world needs.

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/about/operational-groups.html>

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/publications/eip-agri-brochure-operational-groups-collaborate.html>

These (new) digital methodologies should value good land use practices with accurate and accredited measurements and bring these measurements to the market so that landowners can charge for them.

However, there is a gap in connecting the digital methodologies to the land use managers whose primary concern does not necessarily include learning new digital applications. Thus, we need to develop new skill sets for 'bridgers' to connect the farmers and land-use owners with the state of the art carbon monitoring technologies. These bridgers can include consultancy groups (see section 3 for discussion of consultancy services in 3.3.2) and attract the aforementioned groups of young talent and women and can arise from both research and practice domains.

2.4. What is a circular economy?

This report aims to provide a conceptual vision of a circular economy system that can be applied in a real context in the territory. For this reason, the economic framework that will be presented is developed in different case studies with which the team works in LANDMARC. The concept is innovative because it is developed from this circular economy approach, with a value chain made up of multiple elements that pivot on the hub, constituted by the land mitigation technology and practice (LMT), on a regional scale, and applied on a specific territory.

At this point, we can ask two questions to help us better develop and explain this concept.

- How could a circular economy help tackle social and climate challenges effectively?
- Why do we want to integrate LMTs as the core of a rural circular economy system?

The idea is to make the most of the synergies between the smaller, and sometimes weaker, economies that exist in rural areas, and which are directly or indirectly related to using land.

In this initial analysis, we have focused on the direct relationships within the value chain that are closely connected to the consolidated hub centre driven by LMT. However, it is important to acknowledge that there are other goods and services within the rural environment, such as education, healthcare, leisure, and entertainment, that contribute to the overall well-being of the community. In subsequent iterations, these factors can also be linked to the hub. This is because attracting people and other populations back into the rural environment and enabling the development of appealing projects requires not only employment opportunities but also other essential elements that are equally significant.

The idea of a circular economy focuses on optimising commercial, economic, and social interactions within a specific sector. It aims to generate positive synergies, foster innovation and knowledge transfer, and attract new small work groups.

This approach is especially important for revitalising declining rural areas by strengthening their socio-economic fabric. By centralising economic activities and encouraging collaboration, small businesses in rural areas become more resilient and competitive, which is crucial considering their inherent vulnerabilities.

For example, a tree nursery enterprise to reforest degraded agricultural land is stronger if it can have the soil analysis of the agricultural land on which the plantations will be implemented done in a nearby and trusted laboratory, and vice versa.

This example demonstrates the benefits of a linear and two-way commercial relationship. This example demonstrates the benefits of a linear, two-way business relationship between land use managers and companies, or technicians, specialising in different areas of the agricultural sector, where synergy and optimization are already evident. However, if we expand the economic chain to include additional actors the economic chain becomes even stronger and can include: suppliers of organic fertilisers, engineering firms responsible for designing actions, legal advisors assisting with the search for public subsidies, and technicians capable of monitoring the progress and translating natural resource inventories into carbon values. With the inclusion of these experts and resources, economic inputs increase, and the interconnected micro-enterprises complement and reinforce each other. All these actors operate within the same territory and specialise in specific areas of soil-related work, offering solutions to rural, urban, and industrial communities.

This last interaction is necessary to grow the rural economy, and to attract new economic income from the sale of agro-ecosystem services, and this requires innovation and networked entrepreneurship.

2.5. Why LMTs belong at the centre of a rural circular economy

This brings us to our second question; why make LMTs the centre of a rural circular economic system?

This is because strategically placing LMTs at the centre of the circular economy allows the various components of the value chain to revolve around those managing the land directly and thereby the resources, with a direct connection to wider resource management and the business framework of land use. This decision is neither accidental nor arbitrary and is related to the idea of taking advantage and making the most of a social-economic opportunity.

The rural environment faces both social and climate-related challenges, but it can also help provide solutions to other problems – problems created by the urban and industrial environment.

These solutions involve better management of, and obtaining returns from, agro-ecosystem services. To this end, agricultural and forestry production and sustainability must go hand in hand and be compatible with the concepts of climate change adaptation and mitigation.

These agro-ecosystem services are in itself nothing new. However, the innovation is bringing together existing separated services to develop a new integrated system of services with a sustainable circular economy model. Biodiversity, the regulation of the hydrological cycle, the maintenance of natural areas for recreation and leisure, etc., are assets to which society has long attached great value. But now those services for which the economic benefits have always been clear, but whose monetisation has been a challenge, finally have the opportunity to be rewarded in monetary terms due to carbon markets. The proposed economic framework, which places LMTs at the centre of the circular economy, simply takes this factor into account. It places at the centre of the system the value that can actually generate new economic rents, which feed into and enhance the returns of the entire value chain.

The LMTs we consider in this approach are those land uses with the potential to sequester and store carbon, and, crucially, to gain economic rents from doing so, by means of, the carbon credits in the markets. Indirectly, these LMTs cannot be understood without other environmental and social benefits in the agro-ecosystem services such as soil protection, preservation of biodiversity, nature conservation, prevention

of forest fires, maintenance of water and air quality, or strengthening resilience to shocks and extreme climatic events.

Therefore, the conceptual approach and its practical application to the different case studies presented in the next section, is based on a new economic element capable of injecting monetary resources into the rural environment to address both a social and environmental challenge. With minor adjustments, it can benefit as a whole and provide new ideas to address the complex social and environmental challenges facing the agricultural and forestry sectors.

This deliverable aims to create conceptual circular business cases, showcasing their usefulness and potential for the social and environmental benefit of a certain region. Further steps in the development of these business cases will require specification of various elements such as specific technologies for measuring and monitoring carbon. The conceptual character of this deliverable does not require such specifics, which are intentionally left out due to potential intellectual property conflicts.

3. The LMT Hub scheme

3.1. Concept

This deliverable aims to highlight the importance of the LMT Hub concept, explain each of its elements, and apply it to a set of example LMTs. The LMTs considered in the LANDMARC project have the potential of having multiple environmental and social co-benefits. In this section, we propose a scheme to design *LMT Hubs* that harness the full potential of a particular LMT and deliver its maximum impact, in terms of carbon capture, revenue and, more importantly, value (co-benefits).

This generates a business model around a sustainable practice that captures carbon (i.e., the LMT) which has also a wide range of social and environmental co-benefits and the potential of generating multiple additional revenue streams apart from carbon credit trading. In Figure 1, we present the structure of a LMT Hub and its interactions, i.e., the LMT Hub scheme.

Figure 1. Basic LMT Hub structure.

3.2. Elements of the LMT Hub scheme

The core of the scheme is the LMT Hub, which comprises a demand and a supply which interact. These demand and supply couplings form the LMT Hub, which generates a range of outputs (directly tradable or not) and creates feedback loops. These feedback loops could be business opportunities or co-benefits for society or the environment.

3.2.1. LMT Hub

The LMT Hub comprises the core elements of the LMT Hub scheme, which are the demand and the supply:

- **Demand (1):** It is formed by an environmental and a social issue that interact, as environmental problems or disturbances often have a high impact on the local communities, generating a social

concern. For example, a lack of productivity in agriculture such as soil fertility loss (environmental issue) leads to rural depopulation, as people emigrate looking for a more stable source of income (social demand).

- **Supply (3):** It aims to fulfil the demand by using a resource as an input coupled with a technology or practice, which enables the production of outputs (either marketable, such as meat or dairy, or not, such as an improvement in biodiversity).

3.2.2. *Outputs*

The outputs are the products, services or benefits generated by the LMT Hub or any of its feedback loops.

- **Carbon capture (5):** Even though carbon capture already occurs within ecosystems, the application of a LMT will improve carbon capture in ecosystems. This is the reason it is considered both as an input and an output in the LMT Hub scheme.
- **Carbon credits (6):** They are the units assigned to carbon capture to generate a marketable product to this ecosystem service, generating direct revenue.
- **Market products (7):** They are the marketable products generated by the supply. They generate direct revenue.
- **Environment (8):** They are the positive co-benefits for the environment. They generate value, which could be monetized. There is a feedback loop connecting these co-benefits with the initial demand, as they contribute to the solution of the environmental issue of the LMT Hub.
- **Society, community (9):** They are the positive co-benefits for the local communities or the society. They generate value, which could be monetized. There is a feedback loop connecting these co-benefits with the initial demand, as they contribute to the solution of the social issue of the LMT Hub.

3.2.3. *Other elements of building capacity*

There are multiple inputs, including knowledge, tools, stakeholders and policies required to build capacity for new business opportunities. These inputs can contribute to co-benefits that could arise around a particular LMT-Hub, generating circular feedback loops.

- **Knowledge sources (2):** They are needed to properly understand the demand, generate the adequate supply, and enable technologies for monitoring and consultancy. These knowledge sources can be scientific, traditional, Indigenous, etc.
- **Monitoring and consultancy (4):** Monitoring and consultancy jobs are fundamental to monitor carbon capture and verify carbon credits. In addition, they can be used to monitor the impacts of the LMT on the environmental issue, and to scale up the LMT solution to a larger geographical scale. For this, earth observation technologies are key. Appendix 8.1 shows a summary of earth observation technologies applied in LANDMARC.
- **Modelling (10):** Technologies used to scale up the LMT solution to a larger geographical scale. It is linked to monitoring and consultancy jobs. Appendix 8.2 presents a short description of each of the models applied in LANDMARC.
- **Other feedback loops:** Other possible feedback loops created by the LMT Hub include the positive co-benefits created by the LMT application on the local communities, society, and the environment. These co-benefits contribute to the fulfilment of the demand and generate

additional value, aside from the directly marketable products and carbon credits (which generate revenue).

- **Regulatory framework/policies:** This will depend on the site and the LMT, and will impact both the demand and the feasibility of the supply, which will be bounded by regulations and/or supported by policies.

3.3. Workflow for the application of the LMT Hub scheme to a case study

The numbering of each of the elements of the LMT Hub chart in Figure 1 provides an orientation for the application of this scheme to a particular case study. They loosely define the workflow that could be followed when trying to implement this scheme to a case study:

1. **Identify the demand:** Environmental issues or disturbances have an impact on the population, creating a social need. These two elements configure a complex problem that creates demand.
2. **Use multiple knowledge sources:** These sources could be scientific literature, local knowledge, etc. Multiple knowledge sources should be reviewed to help identify the demand, and to aid in subsequent monitoring and consultancy activities (point 4). In addition, the environmental and social issues should be understood in depth to be able to create an adequate supply for the demand (point 3).
3. **Define the supply:** Considering the demand and the information gathered in point 2, a supply could be defined by coupling a resource with a particular technology or practice. In LANDMARC, this supply derives directly from the LMT, which constitutes the technology/practice.
4. **Identify possible monitoring and consultancy activities and other circular business opportunities:** To assess the carbon captured by the implementation of a LMT, monitoring is required. This will inevitably create additional business opportunities for consultants. However, other positive co-benefits, such as the impact on biodiversity, could be monitored as well. The particular business opportunities created by the LMT Hub will depend on the particular case study.
5. **Assess carbon capture:** A carbon capture baseline should be defined according to the knowledge sources and the monitoring activities. The impact of the LMT implementation on it should be estimated as well. This is a basic item for LMT Hub schemes.
6. **Link to carbon credits:** Once assessed, carbon capture (point 5) could be translated to carbon credits and sold in a market. This should be researched according to the knowledge sources and defined through monitoring and consultancy (point 4).
7. **Define market products:** The LMT could generate directly marketable products, which act as a revenue stream.
8. **Assess environmental co-benefits:** Environmental co-benefits derived from the LMT implementation could be assessed and monitored using certain technologies (point 4) depending on the case.
9. **Assess social co-benefits:** The implementation of a LMT will create opportunities for social and local development.
10. **Scale-up:** The final step of the LMT Hub scheme is to assess the possibility of scaling-up the LMT Hub (the solution) to wider geographic areas. For this, consultancy jobs (point 4) will be required, and the LMT Hub scheme could help during the scaling-up process.

4. Forest management and agroforestry

4.1. Spain: Afforestation of degraded agricultural land, adaptation, mitigation, and circular economy (CS13)

The Reforestation of Agricultural Degraded Lands Programme⁶, which began three decades ago in Spain, now has a new focus, related to the carbon sequestration and storage potential of reforested forests that were originally degraded land. Apart from the agri-environmental benefits that formed part of the programme in its beginnings, we can see results today that go beyond the planning of objectives, and which form part of new concepts that would greatly help provide new incentives to investments in degraded land⁷.

The programme has aided soil conservation, desertification, mitigation, degraded area recovery, agroforestry ecosystem restoration and biodiversity enhancement⁸. Regarding mitigation, the reforestations act as carbon sinks, with the potential to become long lasting carbon stores once they become mature forests. In addition, from a social point of view, reforestation of degraded agricultural lands is an opportunity for rural development and the fight against depopulation. Figure 2 shows the outline of a business model encompassing all these benefits.

Figure 2. LMT Hub for CS13, afforestation of degraded agricultural lands.

⁶ <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/desarrollo-rural/temas/programas-ue/periodo-de-programacion-2000-2006/fondos-de-financiacion-de-la-ue-y-programas/introduccion.aspx>

⁷ <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/agriculturaypesca/ifapa/servifapa/registro-servifapa/c0bb1964-fe27-4698-911d-94b173ce10fd>

⁸ <http://7cfe.congresoforestal.es/content/forestacion-de-tierras-agrarias-en-extremadura-0>

4.1.1. LMT Hub

Demand

There is a growing need to find answers to degraded, abandoned agricultural land, mainly as a result of the loss of agricultural income, which leads to the abandonment of rural areas due to the lack of economic opportunities for new generations. This problem is not an isolated one, and is occurring on a sustained basis over time in large rural regions, mainly in the European Mediterranean, but also in other areas historically dominated by various traditional crops. Rainfed cereals or traditional olive groves are two clear examples in the Iberian Peninsula. Apart from agriculture, forestry also suffers from this abandonment of land, as timber production is economically unprofitable.

It is important to highlight that forest fires, increasingly virulent in terms of intensity and surface area in Mediterranean ecosystems, are a real threat to the rural environment and add further uncertainty and risk, together with a worsening of the advance of desertification. We are therefore facing a climatic and environmental cycle with strong social and economic impacts that feeds back leading to land degradation.

Knowledge sources

Faced with these challenges, agricultural engineering, forestry engineering, biological sciences and social sciences (related to migratory movements from rural to urban areas) all provide crucial sources of knowledge which can be combined to offer new business designs that help to combat both environmental and social challenges resulting from land degradation due to land abandonment.

Innovation and technology are also important sources of knowledge. For instance, agricultural digitalisation, can be applied in h forestry to provide solutions for challenges in large rural areas.

But another source of knowledge that is both important and often undervalued, is the local traditional knowledge passed down from generation to generation in terms of land management. This includes knowledge of the land like soil management techniques, botany, efficient water management, the adaptive potential of different agricultural and forestry species to the environment, diseases and pests, and the interactions between different species of fauna and flora. This kind of traditional local, knowledge must be recovered and integrated with new technologies, so that talented young people can use it for the benefit of the territory.

Supply

Proposing solutions to these climatic challenges, and to the threat of desertification in particular, is only possible from a social and economic perspective that generates hope and new opportunities. New economic models that incorporate technology and innovation can be built on the basis of tradition. Reforestation of agricultural land offers opportunities – but only if there is a real commitment over time. It is not enough to simply reforest. These forests must be maintained and integrated, and the economic benefits of them must be tangible and sustained over decades, to generate value and sustainable employment, so that young people can build a life with longer term potential for themselves in rural areas.

Reforestation of degraded agricultural land both fulfils a demand and provides solutions to a real problem and makes sense as the core of a circular economy model. Reforestation requires at least trained agricultural and forestry engineers, technicians and workers; biologists; botanists; pathologists; etc. Other

sciences, such as economics or social sciences, are also included, as they would be crucial to build business models on a larger scale.

4.1.2. Outputs

Market products

Market products include agricultural or livestock outputs from extensive activities in the short (1-2 years) and medium (10-15 years) term, and on an annual basis. Once reforestations has progressed beyond the first few years, the forests provide forest products such as wood, cork or fruit. There is also an additional opportunity in the form of rural and nature tourism in environments that go from being degraded to harbouring pleasant ecosystems for recreation and public use.

Environment

Environmental benefits are at the heart of this model. A direct benefit is the slowing of desertification, thanks to the new forests. But in addition, other values such as biodiversity, agro-ecosystem restoration, wildlife habitat, carbon sequestration and storage, soil protection and regeneration, combating erosion, or improving the resilience of agro-ecosystems to extreme disturbances such as droughts or floods, are part of the long list of improvements for the territory.

Society, community

The social aspects of the model are closely linked to the fight against rural depopulation. The abandonment of agricultural and forestry land has an impact on environmental and climatic problems, and the solutions to the challenges lie in providing new opportunities to generate employment and wealth in rural areas.

Several types of enterprises could flourish. Agricultural and forestry nurseries to produce the necessary plants, irrigation companies, forestry companies for plantations and forestry and subsequent maintenance, machinery and material supply companies, analysis laboratories, fertiliser and phytosanitary suppliers, with a strong component of the implementation of biological and organic systems, or natural pest and disease control.

If reforestation programmes are also aimed at livestock and extensive agriculture, landscape integration and the restoration of ecosystems including rivers and riverbanks, the opportunities grow. In short, it is all part of a land-use plan. But the maintenance of reforestations is essential, as without this maintenance, the model collapses.

4.1.3. Other elements

Carbon capture and carbon credits

The potential for monetisation of agro-ecosystem services is a novelty that did not exist thirty years ago, when the programme for afforestation of agricultural lands began. Today, however, it is an additional source of economic resources, which should be taken advantage of.

The first tangible market that monetises ecosystem services is carbon credits. Reforested forests, which in the past were degraded land, sequester and store carbon on land that previously did not do so. This carbon can be measured and translated into economic values, and provide additional and extraordinary income to reforested land. This additional income is the economic and social impulse for a new territorial model.

Innovation, engineering, new technologies, monitoring, modelling and digitalisation

Engineering, new technologies and innovations in LMTs can support the development of business models to attract young and female talent to rural areas. New technologies help to design reforestations, plan maintenance work, model and organise the territory, manage large databases, or measure biodiversity and sequestered carbon accurately and at reasonable costs. Digitalisation applied to agriculture, forestry and land management is a fast-moving revolution, with multiple cutting edge options, and can even help to configure new models for adding value to tourism services.

Associated business opportunities

The interaction between different technologies, engineering and innovative service companies, or agricultural and forestry companies, can bring synergies to the territory. This creates a growing productive fabric that should be increasingly strengthened. There are direct partnerships in the territory, which make up the circular economy diagram (Figure 2), but also with business sectors outside the rural environment, such as certifiers or auditors, or legal and financial consultancy firms.

These synergies may play out in practice in various ways. First of all, an engineering company is needed to design the plantation. Then a forestry company can carry out the plantations and maintain it. This then creates a market for a forestry nursery, who produces and sells the forestry seeds and plants, as well as for an engineering company to carry out support irrigation and help make it compatible with agricultural activities. In addition, there is also a need for a (start-up) organisation to monitor biodiversity and carbon through a combination of techniques. This allows the certifier to issue carbon credits. The land owner then collects these credits and reinvests in the farm. This whole social, economic, technological, environmental and rural land management model associated with the technology of mitigating land reforestation will only be possible with the drive and firm will of society and policies to maintain investments over time. If reforestation is not sustained over the years, forests will not be a viable outcome 50 years down the line. Long-term thinking must be present in the model.

4.2. Portugal and Spain: Montados and dehesas. Adaptation, mitigation, and circular economy (CS16)

The case study in montados and dehesas explores carbon sequestration potential of these systems in Portugal and Spain. These systems are a High Nature Value (HNV) system that is highly complex due to the interactions between climate, soil, pasture (natural pastures, fertilised natural pastures, and sown biodiverse permanent pastures rich in legumes), trees (e.g., pure or mixed stands of cork oak, holm oak, stone pine), and animals (e.g., sheep, pigs, cows). Montado and Dehesa is one of the most prominent and best-preserved low-intensity farming systems in Europe.

The LMTs implemented in the CS16 are natural capital regeneration, (i.e., cork oak and holm oak regeneration), biodiverse pastures, extensive agriculture reduction, and soil correction. The management system values the natural capital of agroforestry farms by creating good practices in: i) carbon balance; ii) biodiversity; iii) landscape; iv) resilient territories (fire risk reduction); and v) social value. In addition, it creates new business models for farmers in the voluntary carbon market (Figure 3).

Figure 3. LMT Hub for CS16, Montado and Dehesa in Portugal and Spain.

4.2.1. LMT Hub

Demand

Trees in Montado/Dehesa are in decline. This means that there is an urgent need to improve the natural regeneration of trees and therefore an increase of the forest sprout. These systems are generally established in low fertility and high spatial variability soils. The integration of traditional land-use and biodiversity conservation that is characteristic of this system is an example for the longer term management of the countryside.

The Montado and Dehesa region is mainly located in the southern regions of Portugal (Alentejo) and in the South West of Spain (Salamanca, Ciudad Real, Extremadura, Sevilla, Córdoba and Huelva). The regions are characterised by low population density but with high agricultural potential. The lack of water in these regions has been one of the main constraints on its development that prevents the modernization of agriculture and sustainability in public supply. Thus, with a good management plan, these systems can become strong carbon sinks with low GEE emissions. In addition, the regeneration of Montado and Dehesa is the last frontier in the fight against desertification in the region.

Knowledge sources

Montado and dehesa grasslands are generally established in low fertility and high spatial variability soils. However, grassland biomass production can be tripled on the same area of land if certain good management practices are applied. Organic matter can rapidly grow in the soil with small and inexpensive interventions such as low soil inputs correction.

Moreover, planting biodiverse pastures with the correct balance between legumes and grasses, will reduce nitrogen fertilisation, promote CO₂ retention and floristic biodiversity to pollinators as well as overall Mediterranean biodiversity (i.e., fauna and flora). Thus, fertilisation and soil correction should be applied to improve soil fertility and, consequently, productivity/quality of pastures.

In this context, monitoring the grassland quality is a key element in the decision-making process of a farm manager. This is because these grasslands are the main source of animal feed in extensive animal production systems in Portugal and Spain. Pasture nutritional value varies seasonally, annually, and with spatial location and is strongly related to species composition, namely abundance of legumes or grasses and overall plant diversity. Certain botanical species may even be biological indicators of ecosystem degradation situations, such as acid soils or manganese toxicity. The incorporation of Smart Agriculture practices and technologies in the Montado ecosystem represents an important advancement in pasture and landscape management, carbon storage and biodiversity improvement.

Supply

Forestry, agroforestry and agricultural systems are in decline due to a lack of human resources. This is partly due to desertification and low economic attractiveness but is also because they are systems that require a large investment to maintain them, which in most cases does not exist. Farmers/producers bridge this lack of funding by increasing the animal load. This type of management, together with the impact of climate change, causes the system to enter into decline.

To reverse this situation, it is necessary to find new forms of financing so that there is investment in efficient agroforestry management in the conservation of Montado and Dehesa systems with a view to the distant future. For this, it is necessary to involve the different stakeholders, (i.e farmers, forestry producers, academics, policy makers, etc.) so that together they can find solutions that add value to all parties. Such a combination of effort has the potential to create economic benefits for producers, create jobs and attract young people to the interior of the territory.

Valuing the natural capital of agro-forestry companies by creating good practices in carbon balance, biodiversity, landscape, resilient territories (fire risk reduction), and social value will help to improve this

system. But doing so requires investment. An example of funding could be through the creation and promotion of a nationwide voluntary carbon/biodiversity market, i.e., purchase and sale of carbon credits on the voluntary market.

4.2.2. Outputs

Market products

The market products that can emerge from this case study are:

- i) Greater and better cork production;
- ii) Increase in the price of meat (beef, pork, sheep) due to the increase in the quality of the biodiverse natural pastures consumed by the animals;
- iii) Creation of carbon credits to be sold in the voluntary market;
- iv) Eco-tourism potential.

Environment

The Montado and Dehesa region is of high natural value and is located in areas of particular concern for the conservation of birds (Birds Directive, 79/409/EEC), their habitats and conservation of natural habitats in general (Habitats Directive, 92/43/EEC), fauna and flora. The Montado and Dehesa encompasses a notable (bio)diversity of habitats and species that are threatened and that are relevant with regard to achieving the objectives of RN2000, RNAP and REN. Thus, the integration of traditional land use and the conservation of biodiversity that characterises these systems is an example of wise management of the Montado/Dehesa. This integration made use of good management practices of these systems in carbon balance (e.g., biodiverse pastures, soil pH correction, reduction of animal load, forest regeneration) which consequently increases biodiversity, improves the landscape, makes territories more resilient, and adds societal value.

Society, community

Montado/Dehesa is located in semi-arid areas that are susceptible to desertification. They require resilience interventions to combat desertification through natural regeneration and actions that promote increased carbon and nutrient fixation in the soil. The implementation of new methodologies and processes helps to enhance the competitiveness of companies and supports current producers in certifying these services, thereby mobilising more producers. This approach aims to combat demographic desertification by stabilising populations and encouraging new sources of income in the region, ultimately fostering prosperity and resilience in the face of adversity.

4.2.3. Other elements

Carbon capture and carbon credits

One important incentive for farmers and producers in this context is the sale of carbon stocks derived from Montado/Dehesa. These systems offer a distinct advantage in generating a greater amount of financial assets from CO₂ compared to homogeneous forests like eucalyptus plantations. The calculation of CO₂ stocks represents a valuable environmental asset. Once quantified and measured, it can be transformed into a high-value financial asset, enabling a new source of income in an economy that increasingly values

the preservation and maintenance of ecosystems. This is particularly relevant in this region, where the preservation of forest patches is of great importance.

Associated business opportunities

The association of innovative technology methodologies (monitoring, reporting and verification) and various types of stakeholders in regions that are being strongly supported by climate change and desertification, will contribute to better sustainable agricultural and forestry management, preservation and protection of biodiversity, natural capital and ecosystem services. Consequently, the calculation of the estimated CO₂ sequestration will create a new source of income for forest owners and producers through economic incentives to preserve forest, agroforestry and agricultural systems. This fact will boost the creation of an active market for quality and credible Carbon Credits, as an accredited and certified methodology is used, making this whole process quite transparent. The Carbon Credits market is based on a decree-law that creates and promotes the development of a nationwide voluntary carbon/biodiversity market. Thus, the business of carbon credits is created between companies such as AgrolInsider that serve as brokers between polluting companies, industry and others that purchase CO₂ credits and farmers/forestry producers who have credits to sell.

4.3. Kenya: Integrated soil fertility management combined with agroforestry and animal husbandry (CS9)

The LMT implementation considered in the case study in Kenya (CS9) consists of integrated fertility management of farms combined with agroforestry and animal husbandry. This management system has a positive impact on soil fertility, erosion and biodiversity, together with carbon capture through tree establishment. Figure 4 depicts a first approach to a business model based on this LMT, capturing the direct and indirect benefits obtained from its implementation in Kenya.

Figure 4. LMT Hub for CS9 in Kenya, integrated soil fertility management combined with agroforestry and animal husbandry.

4.3.1. LMT Hub

Demand

In Kenya, as in many tropical countries, most soils are highly weathered and thus possess low inherent soil fertility (e.g., cation exchange capacity, water infiltration, weatherable nutrients). This is a serious issue for the cultivation of maize, one of the most important staples in Kenya.

Natural systems usually balance the low soil fertility with a high recycling efficiency of nutrients and high organic matter contents that slowly developed over centuries. Under common cropping schemes, which traditionally consisted of shifting cultivation, (i.e., clearing land, growing maize for a few seasons and then letting the land regenerate) the soils had sufficient time to regenerate from cropping. However, due to increased pressure on land (population growth, development), there is not enough land for traditional shifting cultivation. Many current maize cropping schemes have short or no recovery periods, with limited or no inputs. This is rapidly depleting soil fertility and organic matter and leading to soil erosion in the fallow and establishment phase of maize.

The lack of input is linked to social status. The poorest farmers are usually the ones with the poorest soils, and the lowest yields. They lack the capital for the inputs needed to increase soil fertility and yields and often are trapped in a vicious cycle of decreasing returns on invested labour and decreasing soil fertility.

Knowledge sources

A potential solution is a combination of integrated soil fertility management (ISFM), local knowledge, agroforestry with legume tree species and animal husbandry.

The ISFM component aims at increasing soil fertility, the legume agroforestry trees bring additional nitrogen (N) into the system, through symbiotic N fixation, reducing the need for external inputs (N is often a limiting nutrient in maize cropping systems).

The animal component diversifies the system and provides manure as soil input. While the leaves of the *Calliandra* legume tree in our studies have been shown to bring about some soil organic matter (SOM) formation, the most efficient organic input is farmyard manure. It is thus suggested to use pruning material from legume trees as animal fodder and use their manure as input into the soil. Small amounts of nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) fertilisers may be beneficial, if it is possible for farmers to afford them, yet our results have shown that the most efficient N supply is from manure.

There is also a difference in the responsiveness of soils to inputs. This is best accounted for by local knowledge – that is, the fact that local farmers have a good understanding of which soils respond best to which inputs. Local knowledge is also important in the selection of locally suitable tree species for agroforestry. A potentially rich selection of tree species and knowledge should be available at the world agroforestry centre, which is based in Nairobi.

Supply

Animal manure is very effective in maintaining soil fertility, but feed supply is limited and manure application does not tackle the soil erosion issue. This is where the agroforestry component comes in. An integrated farming approach integrating ISFM supported by local knowledge, agroforestry, and animals can be suitable. Legume tree agroforestry will bring additional N into the system (e.g. *Calliandra*), the tree pruning material can be used as animal fodder together with maize straw, providing a recycling of resources, and additional protein for animals. The animal manure could then be used as soil amendment, as our case study research shows this is most effective. Manure processing could be increased through extension, to minimise losses of nutrients from the animal manures. Where possible, this could be topped up with low amounts of mineral inputs.

4.3.2. Outputs

Market products

As maize is Kenya's main staple, the most important product of the integrated ISFM, agroforestry and animal farming system will be maize for human consumption. This will be enriched by animal products like milk, and meat, which form an important source of a more diversified diet. Further potential for diversification exists in the crops grown (e.g., rotations with legumes) and in the trees, as some mix of legume and fruit trees is also possible.

These diversified products can either be used for the farmers' own consumption, to diversify the food of small-scale farmers, or it can be sold to the market to generate additional income.

Environment

This recommended mixed farming system can benefit the local environment as well as the farmer. Introducing more trees reduces soil erosion. This erosion reduction potential can even be improved by establishing grass strips along the contour lines under the trees (alley cropping system).

Reduced erosion also reduces potential damage to infrastructure due to landslides, or eroded material ending up on the streets. The maintenance of soil fertility can also potentially reduce water runoff and if N is mainly supplied by farmyard manure, the slow N release from manure reduces N-losses to water bodies in areas of more intense inputs.

Finally, the system diversification through the tree and grass components may also lead to a higher biodiversity.

Society, community

The most relevant expected benefit is that small-scale farmers should experience an increase in self-sufficiency and that the legume tree component of the system will reduce their reliance on external N inputs. Also, the diversified farm systems will be more resilient; if one crop or component fails, the others (e.g., the animals) should still yield a benefit. The expected increase of maize yields (or often the avoidance of decrease over time) has another major benefit: Reduced pressure on other land (forests for example) due to the possibility to maintain arable land/cropping cycles for longer, ideally indefinitely. This helps to reduce clearing of natural land, one of the strongest sources of GHG emissions.

4.3.3. Other elements

Modelling

We have developed a local DayCent calibration to ISFM within LANDMARC. With this calibration, we can estimate the potential yield and global warming potential of relevant ISFM practices for all relevant maize growing areas in Kenya. This could then provide figures for creating a longer term business case.

Farmers may use this information to assess the local potential to increase yield, maintain soil organic carbon and reduce GHG emissions, based on our simulations. From this national modelling exercise, we have seen that the yield scaled GHG emissions mainly depend on the yield potential of an area, which is mostly determined by climate, and the soil carbon storage potential, which depends on soil properties and climate. The basis is on meaningful comparisons of the local knowledge on baseline and plausible inputs (e.g., how much manure and N can be made available per ha). For this, we have considered a range from no/current low inputs to maximum stakeholder informed feasible inputs (i.e., manure additions at the level of 0, 0.5, 1 and 2 t C per ha and year, combined with mineral N additions at the level of 0, 30, 60 and 90 kg N per ha and season).

Stakeholders could select a locally feasible baseline and an improved input scheme to see predictions of yield and GHG mitigation potential (maybe an R shiny app could be developed). Agroforestry may also be

modelled in the future with DayCent; but currently, there is no tested calibration for tropical agroforestry with legume trees (and no data to produce one).

Carbon capture and carbon credits

As mentioned above, it is likely that most soils will still be a source of GHG but compared to the baseline (no inputs) GHG will be reduced. The difficulty to monitor and therefore capitalise soil carbon storage has been elaborated above. Also, as Kenya is a middle income country, a functioning carbon credit market may not become available, soon. However, carbon credits for additional trees may be possible, for instance, through REDD+ or transfer payments received as part of the NDC promises that Kenya made.

Associated business opportunities

Monitoring and consultancy

The soil fertility can be measured by simple in-field tests. Additionally, the yield, if several years are considered and different fields are compared, is a representative proxy of soil fertility. Resource use efficiency (yield/input) is usually monitored by farmers who are keenly aware of input costs. Additional value generation, e.g., through the monetisation of carbon capture in the soil could be an option but monitoring is difficult in practice. The first reason is that Kenya is a middle income country, where access to sophisticated labs are scarce. The second reason for this is the inherent small-scale variability, which makes it difficult to detect changes in the field. The third reason is that many fields in Kenya have only been continuously cropped for a few decades, so even under best management, they are usually still losing carbon in absolute terms. ISFM strongly mitigates this loss compared to no inputs (the baseline), but this makes monitoring even more difficult. One way to compensate could be to use predicted carbon sequestration compared to the baseline, based on our modelling exercise with DayCent, which was calibrated to represent ISFM in Kenya. Another simple way to monetize carbon capture would be to focus on additional carbon stored in the legume trees, which can be monitored more easily by tree specific allometric equations.

4.4. Germany: Forest management (CS3)

The German case study exploits the LMT “Improved Forest Management” on existing forests in Germany (Figure 5). It is estimated that changes in forest management practices could have the potential to increase removals by 32⁹ to 68¹⁰ Mt CO_{2eq} by 2050 if applied to the entire forest area. This could be an important contribution to Germany’s goal of achieving GHG neutrality by 2045.

The case study addresses mainly privately owned forests and community forests that makeup 50% of the forest area in Germany. This area matters in particular for market-based instruments put in place for implementing mitigation measures. In state-owned forests, regulatory measures play a more important role.

Figure 5. LMT Hub for CS3, forest management in Germany.

4.4.1. LMT Hub

Demand

In this case study, several challenges have been identified concerning the state of Germany’s forests. The recent drought years 2018-2020 and other disturbances (e.g. insect outbreaks) led to a massive dieback of forests, in particular spruce forests of more than 250,000 ha. Consequently, forest harvest rates increased

⁹ Rüter, Sebastian; Stümer, Wolfgang; Dunger, Karsten (2017): Treibhausgasbilanzen der WEHAM-Szenarien. In: *AFZ-DerWald* (13), S. 30–31. https://www.weham-szenarien.de/fileadmin/weham/Ergebnisse/AFZ_13_17_7_Treibhausgasbilanzen_der_WEHAM-Szenarien.pdf

¹⁰ Böttcher, Hannes; Hennenberg, Klaus Josef; Winger, Christian (2018b): Waldvision Deutschland - Beschreibung von Methoden, Annahmen und Ergebnissen. Öko-Institut e.V. Berlin. <https://www.oeko.de/fileadmin/oekodoc/Waldvision-Methoden-und-Ergebnisse.pdf>

by 20%. About 80% of forest harvest was salvage logging. The increased harvest rate reduced the overall sink capacity of the forest that dropped from about 80 Mt CO₂ a decade ago to 40 Mt CO₂.

The sink contribution of forests in Germany is important for the entire Land Use, Land Use Change, and Forestry (LULUCF) sector that currently forms a net source of 4 Mt CO₂. In 2030 the LULUCF sector is expected to remove 25 Mt CO₂ by the national climate law. The EU LULUCF Regulation requires a similar size of net removals by the sector in 2030. Thus, measures need to be put in place to stabilise and eventually increase removals in forests.

The dieback of forests also offers opportunities to regenerate forests that suffered from low biodiversity (e.g. monocultures with spruce and pine) through establishing mixed forests with more structural diversity. Moreover, there is also the need to address national and EU legislative goals of establishing more areas where natural processes are allowed and timber harvest is reduced or banned.

These demands require investments into forestry in Germany, to regenerate forests, e.g. through planting. But they also create opportunity costs for forest owners if harvest rates are reduced. Currently timber sales are the only income source for forest owners. This income source is highly at risk due to an overflow of bark beetle infested timber. This leads to low timber prices and a narrow focus on the production of coniferous timber in particular. It can be expected that in the future the opportunities for achieving revenue from coniferous timber sales will diminish.

Overall, German forests need to transition towards becoming more climate resilient, German forest owners need more diverse income sources, and the German government needs effective climate protection measures in forests to achieve national and international targets.

Supply

More than 95% of German forests are managed and the majority for wood supply. Other services provided by the forest are often expected to be “by-products”. These include carbon storage, habitat for biodiversity, water retention, good soil quality, and cooling effects.

These services are all expected to improve with better forest management that results in resilient and biodiversity rich forests with benefits for the environment and society. Improvements in forest management needed to achieve these results include: taking forests out of wood production, retaining old trees and dead wood and the establishment of mixed forests with predominantly native tree species. These all imply activities from forest owners and managers that have to be supported and financially rewarded.

Monitoring/Consultancy

There is also a need to actually monitor the outcomes of these activities in order to measure the effects of changes in forest management, form a basis for results-based finance and guarantee that these measures support policy targets.

This implies regular inventories of the forested area. In Germany, national forest inventories are carried out in a 10-years-cycle at a total of more than 47,000 section points. The inventory carried out is organised by a governmental organisation and involves personnel at the juristical, administrative, organisational and

implementation level. However, more frequent and more detailed information is needed to assess progress towards and compliance with national targets but also to identify specific areas where improved forest management needs to be implemented.

Qualified personnel are required not only for improved forest monitoring but also improved forest planning and consultancy for forest owners. Forest owners and managers need consulting on how to achieve the transition towards more resilient future forests through their daily practices.

Knowledge sources

Scientific knowledge is necessary, e.g. regarding forest ecosystems and growth of more mixed and more structured forests compared to monocultures of the past. More practical knowledge is also needed with regard to the activities needed to successfully establish more adapted forest stands with the given resources. The management of game in forests plays a crucial role. Institutional knowledge is essential in order to deal with different levels of administration to allow for effective funding/financial support.

Carbon credit market

Carbon credit markets can provide incentives to forest owners or managers to sell other products than timber. Essentially both market opportunities can be combined. This creates new income sources for forest owners but requires establishing these kinds of markets.

Currently carbon markets are mainly voluntary, and lack minimum standards, consistency and regulation. The involvement of markets with sufficient standards to ensure that improved forest management delivers the demanded services offers the opportunity to mobilise funding from companies seeking for investments in the forestry sector, e.g. for achieving voluntary targets, marketing and corporate social responsibility.

Certification

Certification is an important means to guarantee that market participants comply with the required standards and that the results sold to markets are actually achieved. Certification can build on existing certification schemes in forests. However, information from monitoring and the support from consultancy is necessary to adapt to the requirements of the regulatory framework.

4.4.2. Outputs

Market products

Besides timber (the classic forest product) other products of these forest management practices could include “C storage” and potentially other ecosystem services, which are expected to play an increasingly important role. If the markets are successfully established, these products could become even more important for forest owners than timber sales.

Non-market products

Forests produce products that currently cannot be marketed easily, including the production of oxygen, clean water, and cool air. Other important functions are the retention of water and the forest as a habitat for numerous plant and animal species (biodiversity).

Apart from the ecosystem services, forests are frequently used for recreation, in the form of hiking, biking, hunting, and also for education. Such services could be rewarded through activity-based funding by the state but also voluntary private markets for forest owners that comply with high environmental standards.

Environment

It is expected that the LMT Improved Forest Management will have positive impacts on the resilience of forest ecosystems to better cope with disturbances such as droughts, storms, and insect infestation. Biodiversity will be increased as forests will consist of more diverse tree species offering more habitats to other flora and fauna. Setting forest area aside and retaining old trees and dead wood will increase the overall C stock in the forest.

Government

The LMT of Improved Forest Management will support compliance with national and international targets, such as the EU LULUCF Regulation. However, also other policy targets need to be considered, such as nature conservation, national biomass strategy, and national bioeconomy strategy. Overall, the knowledge base for forestry in Germany needs to be improved to allow for better policy integration and more effective policy implementation.

4.5. Burkina Faso: Agroforestry and cropland management (CS7)

Burkina Faso faces a shortage of quality arable land, as a result of deforestation and a surge in population. Food, water and firewood are in high demand.

The LMT implementation considered in this case study involves agroforestry and cropland management to sustainably maintain the growing population. Figure 6 outlines a business model based on this LMT, capturing the direct economic and indirect benefits on society and the environment derived from it.

Figure 6. LMT Hub for CS13, agroforestry and cropland management in Burkina Faso.

4.5.1. LMT Hub

Demand

Burkina Faso, a landlocked country in West Africa, is facing a number of environmental challenges. Some of the most concerning of these relate to arable land, which is in short supply and often of poor quality of arable land, as a result of deforestation. The country's population has been increasing rapidly in recent decades, and as a result, there has been a growing demand for food, water, and fuelwood. However, the country's natural resources are under pressure due to human activities such as deforestation, land degradation, and overgrazing.

Burkina Faso is one of the poorest countries in the world, and most of its population depends on agriculture for their livelihoods. Unfortunately, the country's agricultural land is shrinking due to the expansion of urban areas and the conversion of land to non-agricultural uses. Moreover, the quality of the remaining arable land is declining due to soil erosion, nutrient depletion, and salinization. As a result, farmers are struggling to produce enough food to feed their families and earn a living.

Deforestation is also a major problem in Burkina Faso, with over 5% of the country's forest cover being lost each year due to the clearing of land for agriculture, grazing, and fuelwood collection. This has resulted in a decline in biodiversity, loss of habitat for wildlife, and increased greenhouse gas emissions. Additionally, deforestation has led to the loss of important ecosystem services such as soil conservation, water regulation, and carbon sequestration. The government of Burkina Faso has recognized the severity of these environmental issues and has implemented policies and programs to address them. However, more needs to be done to ensure the sustainable use of the country's natural resources and to improve the livelihoods of its people.

Knowledge sources

Burkina Faso is a country with a rich agricultural history, and there are several types of knowledge that are important for farming and agroforestry in the region.

Some of the key types of knowledge include:

Traditional knowledge: This refers to the knowledge and practices that have been passed down through generations of farmers in Burkina Faso. This includes knowledge about local crop varieties, soil fertility management, and pest and disease control.

Scientific knowledge: This type of knowledge includes research and experimentation that has been conducted to improve farming techniques and crop yields in Burkina Faso. This can include studies on crop breeding, soil science, and agronomy.

Local knowledge: This refers to the knowledge that is specific to a particular region or community within Burkina Faso. Local knowledge can include information about climate patterns, local crop varieties, and traditional farming practices.

Supply

Table 2 shows a summary of the resources and technology needed in Burkina Faso:

Table 2. Main supply needed for the LMT Hub in Burkina Faso

Sustainable Land Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Promotion of sustainable land management – improving access to climate information ● Cultivation of early or drought-resistant varieties ● Implementation of water and soil conservation techniques ● Practice of integrated soil fertility management ● Development of master plans for water management ● Development of water reservoirs: construction of modern wells, high-flow boreholes, dams; development of ponds; stream diversion ● Development of grazing water sources and points ● Delimitation and development of grazing zones ● Implementation of water-efficient irrigation techniques
Forestry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Implementation of good forestry and agroforestry practices (selective cutting of firewood, assisted natural regeneration, controlled land clearing, etc.) ● Protection of water courses and water sources ● Practice of agroforestry for sustained management of natural resources ● Community and participative management of forest, wildlife and fish resources
Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Diversification of energy sources (solar, wind, biogas) ● Promotion of energy-saving technologies in industry and construction

4.5.2. *Outputs*

Market products

Burkina Faso is an agrarian country, and agriculture is the primary source of income for many people. Some of the main market products from farming and planting trees in Burkina Faso include:

Cereals: Cereals such as maize, sorghum, millet, and rice are the main crops grown in Burkina Faso. These crops are important for food security and are also sold in local and regional markets.

Cotton: Cotton is one of the main cash crops in Burkina Faso, and the country is one of the largest producers in West Africa. Cotton is sold both domestically and internationally, with Europe and Asia being the main export markets.

Fruits and vegetables: Fruits and vegetables such as mangoes, bananas, tomatoes, onions, and peppers are grown in Burkina Faso and sold in local markets and to neighbouring countries.

Livestock: Livestock, such as cattle, sheep, and goats, are raised in Burkina Faso and sold for their meat and dairy products.

Timber and non-timber forest products: Burkina Faso has significant forest resources, and timber and non-timber forest products such as shea butter, honey, and medicinal plants are sold domestically and internationally.

Planting trees: Planting trees in Burkina Faso is becoming an increasingly important market product, as the country faces significant deforestation challenges. Tree planting can provide income through the sale of timber, non-timber forest products, and carbon credits.

Environment, society and community

There are several benefits for society and the environment when implementing sustainable land management practices and reducing deforestation. These benefits include:

Increased food security: Sustainable land management practices can increase soil fertility, crop yields, and diversify crops, which can help to improve food security and reduce the risk of hunger and malnutrition.

Climate change mitigation: Reducing deforestation and implementing sustainable land management practices can help to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and mitigate the impacts of climate change. Trees absorb carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and store it in their biomass, and the soil can also store carbon.

Improved water quality and availability: Sustainable land management practices can improve soil health and reduce erosion, which can improve water quality and availability. Trees and other vegetation help to retain water in the soil, which can improve groundwater recharge and reduce the risk of flooding.

Biodiversity conservation: Deforestation and unsustainable land management practices can lead to the loss of biodiversity, including plant and animal species. Sustainable land management practices can help to conserve biodiversity by preserving natural habitats and restoring degraded ecosystems.

Increased income and employment opportunities: Sustainable land management practices can create income and employment opportunities for local communities, including through the production and sale of agricultural products, non-timber forest products, and ecotourism.

Overall, implementing sustainable land management practices and reducing deforestation can have significant social, economic, and environmental benefits, helping to improve the well-being of local communities and conserve natural resources for future generations.

4.5.3. Other elements

Associated business opportunities

Monitoring and consultancy

The business opportunities of current and potential monitoring and consultancy services in Burkina Faso include:

Agricultural extension services: These services are provided by the government and NGOs to provide farmers with information and training on farming practices, crop management, and marketing opportunities.

Soil testing services: These services are offered by private and public sector organisations to test the fertility and health of the soil, and provide recommendations on fertilisers, lime, and other soil amendments.

Pest and disease monitoring: Various organisations provide monitoring services to identify pest and disease problems that may affect crops. They also provide advice on how to manage these issues.

Market information services: These services provide farmers with information on prices, demand, and supply in local and regional markets, helping farmers to make informed decisions on what crops to grow and when to sell them.

Carbon credits services: These services provide farmers with information on carbon sequestration, and how to adapt farming practices to improve the CO₂ sink.

5. Agriculture

5.1. Nepal: Improving rice production (CS15)

The LMT implementation considered in the Nepal case study (CS15) consists of improving sustainable rice production. Figure 7 outlines a business model based on sustainable rice production, capturing the direct economic and indirect benefits on society and the environment obtained from its implementation.

Figure 7. LMT Hub for CS15, improving rice production in Nepal.

5.1.1. LMT Hub

Demand

The increasing cost of production, shortage of labour during peak periods, and erratic onset of rainfall in rainfed rice cultivation have created a demand for different improved rice cultivation methods in Nepal.

Knowledge sources

There is potential to establish a rice knowledge exchange hub for dissemination, sharing and co-learning of rice LMTs, that can integrate scientific and indigenous knowledge. Indigenous knowledge for traditional rice varieties and traditional farming practices including soil fertility management (eg. use of organic matter, crop residue, animal manure and composting techniques), traditional water management, and traditional disease and pest management practices. Scientific knowledge is required to measure and monitor carbon and knowledge on new rice management methods.

Supply

Technology

Dry seeded rice is a LMT which involves rice crop establishment with a direct seeding method, instead of a transplanting method.

Policy

Although there is no direct policy for rice LMTs, environmentally friendly agricultural practices have been mentioned in the updated NDC of Nepal. The government's incentives for farm machinery purchases also creates a favourable environment to implement rice LMTs.

5.1.2. Outputs

New business model development: Different new opportunities arise such as eco-rice, farm machinery custom hiring centres and new rice husk supply businesses for green energy.

5.1.3. Other elements

Modelling

Scaling up rice LMTs hub at the district levels by establishing district rice LMT hub (DRH), and regional hubs in each of the seven provinces.

Carbon capture and carbon credits

Carbon credits can be earned through government incentives and international carbon markets that give value to the efforts of small farmers in reducing carbon emissions, increase biodiversity (by saving Indigenous rice varieties), and improve water quality (by reducing nitrogen leakage and percolation).

Associated business opportunities

Monitoring

Monitoring and valuing carbon, biodiversity, water quality for community-based rice LMT implementation (note: due to the small size of farms such services for individual farms are not feasible).

Institutional capacity building

- Support for development of local and national policies on production and marketing of eco labelled rice that could be sold at the premium prices.
- Training of human resources in government, NGOs and local communities for promotion of rice LMTs.
- Establishment of eco-rice fund via joint effort of government, INGOs and private sector for providing incentive to rice farmers.

5.2. Canada: Land restoration and food production

Land degradation due to oil extraction is a concerning problem in Canada. The LMT implementation considered in this case study consists of the establishment of community greenhouses to aid boreal forest restoration and potentially wetland (muskeg in the Indigenous Cree language) recovery as well as to promote food security through building greenhouses for food production. Figure 8 outlines a business model based on this LMT, capturing the direct economic and indirect benefits on society and the environment obtained from its implementation.

Figure 8. LMT Hub for the case study in Canada, land restoration and food production.

5.2.1. LMT Hub

Demand

Local Indigenous communities require a clean environment and secure access to food to thrive, particularly since there is poor air quality and concerns that toxic substances from industry might also impact soil health. Significant degradation of the local environment and socioeconomic inequalities created by colonisation, including pushing Indigenous communities off their traditional lands, and such inequalities have been exacerbated by oil sands extraction.

Knowledge sources

Knowledge for this LMT is obtained from established Western scientific knowledge on the matter and traditional ecological knowledge obtained directly under the guidance of senior community members.

Supply

Greenhouses to produce food and seedlings are needed for restoring the boreal forest (forest and wetlands), which will generate carbon offset credits to generate revenue to fund the venture. Also, increasing biodiversity, clean water, clean air, and a healthy ecosystem supplies the local community services to improve their quality of life. The people/groups involved are: The Indigenous communities directly involved in planting and knowledge sharing, Indigenous youth education programs to help younger generations to learn from elders' knowledge of land management and to also learn about land-based technology and practices from Western science for the future. LANDMARC can bring in technical knowledge and application while construction and tech companies can help build customised greenhouses for the community's needs.

5.2.2. Outputs

Market products

Reduction of costs associated with food supply and improving access to health food which is not currently available within the community. Overall health and wellbeing can be improved if the green house acts as a community centre or anchor for communities activities, and later on potential tourism/recreation revenues if the greenhouse hub concept can be scaled up. If the concept can be scaled up the community can provide consulting services to surrounding Indigenous communities to replicate the model.

Environment

Regeneration of muskeg (wetlands), replantation of trees, restoration of soil nutrients, increased biodiversity, cleaner waterways, reduction of intensity of wildfires.

Society, community

Employment for community members, education and tech-based learning for the community's youth, year-round secure food supply, acknowledgement and the possibility of practising traditional ecological knowledge and subsistence practices.

5.2.3. Other elements

Modelling

We intend to evaluate the case study for the 2030, 2050, and 150 years timelines considering the seventh-generation principle. For long-term viability, we are considering macroeconomic modelling (E3ME) to verify the financials, ALCES for land use, and LIDAR data for above-surface biomass and water. Community-based monitoring programs would be incorporated to monitor biodiversity and wildlife.

Carbon capture and carbon credits

Credit generation within a voluntary market at first. Then it is expected that the project could take part in the federal and/or provincial framework for carbon offset trading, given that nature-based solutions are included in the protocol.

Associated business opportunities

Monitoring and validation of CO₂ and biodiversity (consultancy services)

Soil sampling, drone survey, and satellite imagery would be used to monitor biodiversity, photosynthetic activity and carbon removal from food crops and plants, muskeg regeneration and replantation of forests. Activity to be done by a contractor or partner in the venture.

5.3. The Netherlands: Sustainable agriculture

Livestock farming in The Netherlands has a large claim on the use of scarce land. In 2022, about 2.2 million ha of land (or 54% of total land use) was used for agricultural purposes. A sizable part of this arable land 1.16 million ha (54%) was used as grassland and cultivation of other feed crops for cattle (e.g., fodder maize). Both the cattle sector and pig sector are key contributors to national NH₃ and CH₄ emissions. This livestock farming practice is no longer considered to be sustainable in the long-run due to several environmental (e.g., biodiversity, soil subsidence, GHG/NH₃ emissions) and social (e.g., animal/human health, housing shortage, land scarcity and flood risks) issues. As a result, a transition strategy is needed for (dairy) cattle and pig farmers to make better, more sustainable end/or alternative use of their land, livestock, and biomass resources to reduce their negative impacts on the environment, while at the same time contributing to a range of social, economic, and environmental goals.

We propose three transition scenarios/business cases:

1. **Base case:** dairy cattle and pig farming remain at the same level of productivity and do not switch away from traditional (intensive) livestock farming practices. This will entail a continuation of existing livestock management practices with associated negative environmental and social impacts (e.g., emissions and future costs of soil subsidence and further environmental decline).
2. **New 1 - scaling nature-based solutions:** Planting additional trees outside forests (as agroforestry or as afforestation) and rewetting organic soils will be implemented. The subsequent land claim for scaling these nature-based solutions could be synergetic with the envisioned deliberate (planned/forced) reduction of the livestock sector. Such reduction of livestock herds will automatically reduce the related NH₃/CH₄ emissions. Both rewetting and tree planting will reduce the land available for feed (grass / maize) production or will lower the overall yields per hectare, requiring more extensive livestock management practices for cattle (or additional feed imports).

Business case: the business case for rewetting is uncertain as nationwide rewetting may be implemented without clear plans for farm compensation. Also, the business case for agroforestry and afforestation is marginal and risky, particularly in the start-up phase of around 5 years, and because new supply chains and market demand for new bio-based products are not well established. In addition, the valorisation strategy (which incentives to pick and combine) is unclear (see Figure #6). Rewetting practices are most suitable in the lower lying Northern and Western parts of The Netherlands with higher shares of organic/peat(y) soils, while tree planting (for agroforestry or afforestation) is more suitable in the Southern and Eastern parts of the country with higher shares of sandy and clay type soils (see Figure #10).

3. **New 2 - scaling engineered solutions:** Anaerobic digestion of animal manure and post-treatment of digestate is used to reduce CH₄, NH₃ emissions from livestock, to produce renewable energy (biogas), liquid CO₂ and organic fertilisers to replace fossil equivalents (see Figure #7). The scale of deployment (manure availability) will largely depend on the expected size of the dairy and pig herds. The current political debate considers planned reductions (even with possible forced buyouts) of the livestock sector ranging from 10-50%.

Business case: Currently, the business case for biogas-CCUS is highly uncertain within the political landscape which intends to proactively reduce the size of the livestock sector, and fragmented

policy regime for valorisation (see Figure #6). In this situation the expected decline in domestic food production may be dampened.

We anticipate that a most plausible scenario will entail a combination of the above three scenarios (figure 9), where certain highly productive regions, where soil subsidence is less of an issue, and no Natura2000 zones are nearby will retain intensified cattle/pig farming (base case). Others could retain a certain level of semi-intensive (dairy) cattle farming, which can be combined with anaerobic digestion of animal manure (scenario 3). This would also free up land to build additional houses and infrastructure but may limit land available for expansion of natural areas (e.g., afforestation). Other areas may switch to a more extensive type of livestock farming system to limit environmental issues, expand land available for rewetting and tree planting (scenario 2).

Figure 9. LMT Hub for a case study in The Netherlands, sustainable agriculture.

5.3.1. LMT Hub

Demand

Environmental issues

The large claim on land and sizeable (dairy) cattle sector (3.8 mln. cattle, 7th largest bovine herd size in EU) in the country comes with a series of environmental issues of which the main ones are:

- **Ammonia emissions:** Due to the high livestock density in the Netherlands (incl. pig, poultry, and cattle)¹¹, the Dutch livestock sector in general is a large contributor to NH₃ emissions (86% of total

¹¹ Highest amount of livestock units per hectare in the EU, see: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Agri-environmental_indicator_-_livestock_patterns

national NH₃ emissions). Of total agricultural NH₃ emissions about 52% originates from cattle. NH₃ emissions are linked to nitrogen deposition on natural areas which is considered to significantly contribute to ongoing biodiversity losses. Bringing NH₃ emissions down to preserve/improve the state of existing (protected) habitats is one of the dominant political drivers within the country.

- **Soil subsidence:** Due to decades of drainage of organic/peat(y) soils The Netherlands has been able to build up and sustain a sizeable (dairy) cattle industry. Drainage of soils allowed for more intensified cattle farming and cultivation for roughage feeds on soils that are normally not suitable for any type of land-based farming¹². The continued drainage is no longer sustainable in the long run, mainly due to ongoing soil subsidence. This process is intensified by climate change, where prolonged droughts, combined with shorter, but more intensified precipitation periods create difficulties for water management and buffering. The different future water management and climate scenarios show that by 2100 there are some areas which will experience soil subsidence levels of well over 60cm¹³. This will have cause massive damages and repair costs for all houses, infrastructure, industries, and other economic activities in those regions. Sustaining the current state of intensified cattle farming practices is closely linked to maintaining the practice of continued drainage of organic/peat(y) soils.
- **GHG emissions:** The agricultural sector emits a little below 16% of total national GHG emissions. However, it is a major emitter of CH₄ (76% of total CH₄) and N₂O (64% of total N₂O) emissions, and only 5,6% of total CO₂ emissions. N₂O emissions are mainly related to the use of both organic and mineral fertilizers used in agriculture. CH₄ emissions mainly originate from livestock (pig and cattle), as enteric emissions (cattle represents about 90% of enteric CH₄) and emissions from manure management (pig and cattle represent resp. 60% and 40% of manure management emissions).

Social issues

The above environmental issues also translate into a series of social issues. NH₃ emissions cause decline in biodiversity and air pollution which is causing a range of health care related issues¹⁴. Continued soil subsidence will cause significant multi-billion economic, and social damage to buildings and infrastructure¹⁵. Already, many people in the country are experiencing damage to their buildings as a result of this¹⁶.

In addition to these social issues, there is also a structural housing shortage¹⁷ in the country that increases the need for building new houses for the country's residents. This will put an additional claim on land,

¹² Paludiculture and aquaculture type farming systems may be viable.

¹³ <https://www.klimaat-effectatlas.nl/nl/bodemdalingsvoorspellings-kaarten>

¹⁴ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/newsroom/news/premature-deaths-due-to-air-pollution-continue-to-fall-in-the-eu-more-efforts-needed-to-deliver-a-toxic-free-environment>

¹⁵ <https://www.pbl.nl/publicaties/dalende-bodems-stijgende-kosten>

¹⁶ This map (<https://www.klimaat-effectatlas.nl/nl/risicokaarten-funderingen>) provides a 'risk map' for building foundation damage.

¹⁷ <https://www.capitalvalue.nl/en/news/housing-shortage-in-the-netherlands-will-rise-to-415000-homes-in-2024>

where each square metre is already in use, or where vast areas of land mainly in the lower lying coastal and river regions are already exposed to significant flood risk¹⁸. Aside from that the ongoing energy transition is also putting an additional claim on scarce land for the production of renewable electricity (mainly onshore solar photovoltaic systems).

Knowledge sources

Translating stakeholder preferences to qualitative storylines

Stakeholder knowledge is key to appropriately identifying the demand and developing a working LMT Hub. Table 3 shows a draft of a qualitative storyline for The Netherlands, identifying measures and actions from interviews. This information will also be important for the modelling stage (step 10, figure 12).

¹⁸ <https://www.atlasleefomgeving.nl/kaarten?config=3ef897de-127f-471a-959b-93b7597de188&activeTools=layercollection,search,info,bookmark,measure,draw,koeltorens&activateOnStart=layercollection&layerFilter=Alles%20tonen&gm-x=149999.9999999999&gm-y=459999.9999999998&gm-z=3&gm-b=1544180834512,true,1;1578048914305,true,0.8;1554714406473,true,0.8;1638290151507,true,1;1638290151497,true,1;1638290151486,true,1;1638290151475,true,1>

Table 3. Qualitative Storylines of implementation for each of the LMT options in The Netherlands

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who pays? Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: <i>Business as Usual</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuation of existing (intensive) livestock farming practices, with associated land use, economic benefits, and social-environmental costs (0 to -5% decline can be assumed). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social-environmental costs are borne by society and ecosystems. Complex system agro-food production (consumers, farmers, supermarkets, agro-food companies, guided by policy frameworks) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scenario incompatible with a range of air quality, biodiversity, water, climate policies and strategies

**Scenario 2:
Scaling nature
based solutions**

- | | | |
|--|---|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of cattle (& pig) herd size by 30-50% (range) to reduce environmental impacts and free up land for other uses. To achieve targets, this should already be achieved by 2030 or 2035. • Expansion of rewetting organic / peat(y) soils in Northern and Western (coastal) provinces to keep carbon in soils, limit (damage of) soil subsidence and preserve / improve biodiversity. This could technically be scaled up rather fast by 2030-2035, simply by limiting draining the country via existing water infrastructure. • Expansion of agroforestry and afforestation in the Southern and Eastern part of the country on sandy/clay soils to increase carbon storage in trees (and materials) while improving biodiversity. Agroforestry may scale up a bit faster as hedgerows and planting of productive trees, fiber crops can be done faster. Full scale implementation by 2050 according to a linear trajectory should be feasible. Afforestation targets by 2050 could be achieved, but phase-in will likely start slower as | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Livestock farmers and the linked agro-food sector will see significant decline in revenue/profits. Compensation for these losses (or finance for buy-out schemes for farmers) will come from the public budget. • Rewetting can be implemented by farmers / landowners (parcel level), but also at subregional level (for each catchment area 'polder' by regional water boards). This is done by increasing water levels. In case farmers execute this, funding may come from private sector or EU agricultural funds. When done by water boards, extra water management costs may be charged to society (to fund rewetting and/or compensate farmers). This may be funded through avoiding future damage costs. • Agroforestry is likely implemented by farmers in collaboration with expert third parties. In most cases no land acquisition needed as farmland is already owned. Farmers will need to invest, which | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 30-50% reduction of livestock sector (question of balance between poultry, pig, cattle) to meet 2030-2035 - NH3 emission reduction target. • Rewetting target = -1 MtCO₂-eq. emissions from peat soils by 2030 (current level at 4-7 MtCO₂-eq. per year). • Agroforestry expansion is set at a range of 7.000-25.000 ha by 2030. <i>Dutch Forest Strategy, the total climate impact of agroforestry is quantified as part of the sector goal "trees, forest and nature" with 0.4 Mton CO₂ and 0.8 Mton CO₂ ('ambitious goal') in 2030. However, it is not clear yet how much of the aimed GHG emissions are assigned to non-agroforestry in this sector such as landscape elements. According to (Lesschen et al., 2021), agroforestry could contribute to 0.1 Mton CO₂, however, assuming</i> |
|--|---|---|

	<p>massive amounts of seedlings need to be planted, land needs to be purchased (legal procedures).</p>	<p>can be funded by the market (new other market products or carbon market), or public funds (EU CAP/forestry funds).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Afforestation is likely implemented by semi-public nature conservation / forestry agencies. Will entail costs for land acquisition / buyouts. Other costs involve cultivating, buying, and planting seedlings/trees. Land acquisition costs are likely to come from public sources (although there are some private funds also buying land). Funds for planting trees to be funded through a mix of public and private schemes (e.g., CAP/forest funds + carbon market) 	<p><i>a more ambitious target of 25,000 ha in 2030 compared to 7,000 ha mentioned in the Dutch Forest Strategy.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forest expansion outside Natura2000 (NNN) zones target for 2030 set at 19.000 ha. <i>Overall forest sector target includes an increase (18,000 ha) to be realized in the so-called Nature Network the Netherlands (NNN), which includes all Dutch Natura 2000 sites, and partly (19,000 ha) outside this network in forests that are private property.</i>
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<p>Scenario 3: Scaling engineered solutions</p>	<p>Reduction of cattle (& pig) herd size by 5-29% (range) to reduce environmental impacts and free up land for other uses. To achieve targets, this should already be achieved by 2030 or 2035. Significant expansion of manure treatment facilities (farm-level and industrial scale plants) for production of biogas (biomethane / bio-LNG, organic fertilizers (RENURE) and captured liquid/compressed CO₂. Could theoretically be deployed to all liquid cattle/pig manure captured in stable systems (54,1 mln ton cattle manure, 8,9 mln ton pig manure (link)). Currently, about 5-10% of all animal manure is undergoing some form of manure treatment. Biogas sector has seen a slow down (link) of new production coming online (0,23 BCM in 2022, 4% growth rel. to 2021). Large-scale (pig manure) plants could scale up more rapidly, relative to development of farm-scale biogas systems or biogas hubs.</p>	<p>Livestock farmers and the linked agro-food sector will see significant decline in revenue/profits. Compensation for these losses (or finance for buy-out schemes for farmers) will come from the public budget. Farming sector, energy and fertilizer sector will be most involved in implementation. Energy components can be funded through a range of renewable energy subsidy schemes (e.g., feed-in premium, co-firing under EU ETS, renewable transport fuel tradable certificates) for biogas and even a green gas blending target (link) may be implemented. Also, several market-based schemes for using organic fertilizers, carbon markets may apply.</p>	<p>5-29% reduction of livestock sector (question of balance between poultry, pig, cattle) to meet 2030-2035 - NH₃ emission reduction target. Domestic policy target for biogas/green gas production is 2 BCM by 2030 (link). Also the EU has specific strategy to increase production of biomethane (link). No quantified target for circular agriculture, but nutrient (N, P, K and SOC) recycling can be improved significantly by enabling manure treatment to produce organic fertilizers. However, use of organic fertilizers from animal origin has been capped by EU-law. More recently Dutch farming has lost rights (link) to use 230-250 Kg animal manure N per ha. By 2026 it will be limited to 170 Kg N per ha, current derogation will be gradually phased out until 2026. This is expected to increase the use of chemical fertilizers to maintain productivity. RENURE (link) fertilizers are becoming more important with increasing prices for gas and chemical fertilizers.</p>
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6. Biogas

6.1. Indonesia: Biogas implementation for agroforestry farmers (CS12)

The LMT implementation considered in the case study in Indonesia (CS12) involves the implementation of biogas for agroforestry farmers.

Biogas has a positive impact on carbon through both sequestration and emissions reduction. Figure 10 outlines a business model based on this LMT, capturing the direct and indirect benefits on society and the environment obtained from its implementation.

Figure 10. LMT Hub for CS12, Biogas implementation for agroforestry farmers in Indonesia.

6.1.1. LMT Hub

Demand

Environmental issues

There are several environmental issues that Indonesian farms face:

1. Unmanaged agricultural waste: particularly manure and agricultural waste such as cacao husks or coffee skins. When left untreated, this waste can contribute to soil degradation and water pollution, as well as emit GHG such as methane, nitrous oxide, and carbon dioxide (CO₂).
2. Chemical fertilisers, which can have negative impacts on soil health and the surrounding ecosystem. Synthetic fertilisers can pollute waterways and contribute to soil acidification, which can decrease soil fertility and ultimately harm crop yields. Furthermore, the lack of proper waste management and the use of synthetic fertilisers can result in nutrient imbalances in the soil, which can further harm the ecosystem and negatively affect crop yields. Meanwhile, in Indonesia, the government still gives the subsidy scheme for the chemical fertiliser.

Social issues

The environmental issues are directly linked to various social issues faced by the farmers. Firstly, farmers who raise cattle or grow crops like cacao often have a large amount of organic waste that can be difficult and costly to dispose of.

Secondly, many farmers in rural areas still rely on traditional stoves that burn wood or other biomass fuels, which can cause death from indoor air pollution.

Finally, farmers need economic incentives to engage in sustainable land management practices like agroforestry. Basic needs such as fertilisers and gas are becoming more expensive, so climate-smart practices are deemed to be less economically viable than their inorganic counterparts.

Addressing these challenges or needs (both social and environmental) for local farmers through sustainable technologies can help to create a more climate-resilient system that benefits both the environment and local communities.

Knowledge sources

Addressing these issues would require technologies or practices that meet the farmers' needs. This requires combining knowledge from the following sources:

- Farmers' knowledge (champion farmers): Traditional practices were deemed to be climate-smart before the industrialization of agriculture. Technology must match with farmers' capacity and also needs.
- Engineering knowledge (local): Technology design must be ergonomic and user-friendly.
- Research knowledge for policies, incentives, funding availability, voluntary market, and business case: In the case of scaling up, many research avenues need to be explored from financing via the carbon market to policymaking to synergize with national targets.

Combining scientific and local knowledge in this way, will allow the most appropriate technology/practice to be identified. In this case, one good option looks to be portable biogas for agroforestry farmers (coffee and cacao). This meets farmer's needs, which are:

- Easy-to-install;
- Easy-to-maintain;
- Affordable for farmers.

Supply

As for the supply, agroforestry farmers who use portable biogas will get two main benefits for land mitigation:

- Soil carbon enhancement from bioslurry/organic fertiliser; and
- Co-benefits: clean energy and waste management.

6.1.2. Other elements

Associated business opportunities

Monitoring and consultancy

To maintain the biogas, there is a need to apply good monitoring, reporting, and verifying (MRV) practices by applying:

- In-situ measurement (EO-Earth Observation/RS and chemical and biogenic soil assessment); and
- Future assessment through energy, climate, and land models (E3ME, Landshift, and ALCES).

By applying good MRV practices, biogas can meet farmers' needs and have more additional values (i.e., incentives from carbon offset, employment opportunity, health and life improvement, and gender equity). Hence, there will be a better business case to be presented to funders.

6.2. Sweden: Emission avoidance combining BECCS and biochar (CS11)

The portfolio of LMTs in the Swedish Case Study considers BECCS and biochar. Deployed together, the two technologies are expected to help the country reach net-zero emission by 2045 and negative emissions onwards.

This section is a first approach to creating a business model considering the portfolio technologies (Figure 11), their effects in terms of supply and demand, the required services and tools to monitor their use, their expected positive effects in the society and the environment and the probable marketable products.

Figure 11. LMT Hub for CS11, BECCS and biochar in Sweden.

6.2.1. LMT Hub

Demand

Sweden has an energy demand both from electricity and heating services which can be provided with the use of biomass. Combustion processes for energy production can release CO₂ emissions and pollution to the atmosphere. This, in turn, can lead to health problems for those exposed to the emissions. Biomass sourcing for energy production can represent price fluctuations for the final user, making electricity and heating expensive.

Soil quality for agricultural production, including biomass, can be affected by intensive agricultural practices. Additionally, soil degradation is also present in urban areas and is reflected in poor urban landscapes characterised by unhealthy urban gardens. This can impact farmer communities and urban inhabitants.

Based on this, there is a demand for alternatives that decrease the negative effects of energy production and improve soil quality.

Knowledge sources

To apply BECCS and biochar services, it is very important to know what the size of the energy demand is. It is therefore key to have access to data about energy demand from heat/energy service providers. Similarly, it is important to account for the biomass available to be transformed into energy.

Lastly, emission storage can only be achieved if the hub has access to knowledge of stakeholders aware of the size of CO₂ underground storage alternatives and how to access them.

Supply

In this case study, biomass is the starting point for energy production and supply. To decrease the social and environmental issues previously presented, the use of BECCS and biochar is proposed as a solution. BECCS allows heat and electricity production while emissions are captured and stored. Biochar permits re-purpose biomass residues and to produce energy.

In the case of BECCS, relevant stakeholders include energy producers that operate Combined Heat and Power (CHP) units, able to treat the exhaust emissions with catalysts that enable transporting CO₂ emissions to underground storage.

Biochar production involves stakeholders with relation to residual biomass, including farmers, municipalities with access to residual biomass and communities with access to residual biomass. By means of a low oxygen atmosphere, residual biomass that goes through a pyrolysis process stores the carbon present in it. The result of pyrolysis is a carbon rich biochar and process energy.

BECCS and biochar can supply energy in the form of heat which can be a core revenue generation activity if it is connected to a district heating system.

6.2.2. Outputs

Market products

In addition to the revenue from carbon credits stemming from BECCS and biochar (section 8.3.2), energy and electricity generated in each process can be sold to the grid and to district heating.

Biochar is also frequently used as a soil amendment, which benefits agricultural production. Its physical properties make it ideal for improving degraded soils. Additionally, biochar can also be used as an additive to construction materials, a use that does not interfere with its ability to store carbon.

Environment

The benefits of using BECCS and biochar together aim to tackle the environmental issues previously presented. Benefits include circularity, soil improvement and improved landscape, as well as enhanced air quality for civil society through emissions' storage.

Society, community

Taken together, BECCS and biochar can provide a number of benefits for the community. For example, both can stimulate new businesses and job creation throughout the biochar supply chain. This can be done by obtaining the biomass, processing it and transporting heat, emissions or biochar.

Other benefits stemming from the combined production of BECCS and biochar include improving soil management through the involvement of community stakeholders and farmers that make use of biochar in their crops/urban gardens.

6.2.3. Other elements

Modelling

Feasibility of the implementation of BECCS and biochar should be evaluated using econometric modelling. This allows the evaluation of the project feasibility and its economic implications.

Carbon capture and carbon credits

Carbon credits are the mechanism to award value to the emissions that are being avoided, in the case of biochar, and that are being stored, in the case of BECCS. In Sweden, policy instruments include the establishment of voluntary markets for emissions trading, tax benefits associated with emissions reduction and emissions quota and certificate exchange. These instruments can stimulate the use of the technologies.

Associated business opportunities

Monitoring and validation of carbon dioxide and biodiversity (consultancy services)

Monitoring for the BECCS and biochar portfolio is proposed to have four main components. Both technologies should monitor how many CO₂ emissions are stored and their permanence in time. As part of the production process, energy consumption and production should be also monitored. These two measurements allow the validation of the emission storage and energy use.

In the case of biochar, its use in soil can also be monitored through the measurement of crop or vegetation increase where employed.

6.3. Ukraine: A sustainable biogas energy system and organic agriculture

The LMT portfolio for Ukraine consists of organic farming, agroforestry (shelterbelts), reduced tillage, and bioenergy. This is combined with the base scenario (considering the development of the agricultural sector, urbanisation, nature protection, etc.).

Amid the ongoing climate change, the war in Ukraine, from February 24, 2022, has intensified the consequences of soil cover destruction. Soil disturbances, including damage from cruise missiles and shrapnel, contaminate the land and accelerate the loss of carbon from the soil and makes the land (temporarily) unsuitable for agriculture. An interim assessment of greenhouse gas emissions in four key areas directly caused by the war determines that emissions amount to at least 100 million tons of CO_{2eq} only in the first seven months of hostilities¹⁹. This is comparable to the annual emissions of a country such as Belgium²⁰.

The combined factors of climate damage and the war in Ukraine's agricultural sector have strongly impacted the world's food security. Ukraine has a longstanding track record of providing essential nutrition to many different parts of the world. The associated agricultural waste streams provide an opportunity for the energy system via biogas energy systems. Decentralised biogas systems will help address the current energy security crisis in Ukraine and contribute to addressing climate change by providing clean, sustainable, resilient energy systems.

Ukraine has a large territory of black soil (dark grey, dark chestnut, dark grey podzolic, and chernozems²¹). Chernozems are one of the most widespread types of black soils in Ukraine. Chernozem soils of Ukraine are characterised, in general, by average (2-3%) and high (3-4%) humus content in the arable layer. The soil area with this content is 16.4 mil. ha, or about half of the arable land. The depth of Ukrainian soil profiles varies very widely, and for chernozem soils, depending on geographical, climatic, and other factors, it is up to 170 cm. Stocks of humus (SOC) in the main Ukrainian soils also vary widely: humus 100-720 t/ha, SOC 60-420 t/ha²².

We propose the following scenario as a possible business model for Ukraine. The scenario is a balanced mix scaling biogas engineering solutions and organic farming. ; This will allow the use of processed waste from biogas production as organic fertilisers for farming, thereby increasing the yield and quality of organic products and reducing carbon. In turn, independent biogas stations will help ensure the energy security of each region separately (Figure 12).

¹⁹ [Ministry of Environmental Protection and Natural Resources of Ukraine](#)

²⁰ [Belgium: CO₂ Country Profile](#)

²¹ [The black gold of Ukraine and the most fertile soils in the world](#)

²² [Ukrainian chernozems as a factor in global food security and resilience of agriculture to climate change](#)

Figure 12. LMT Hub for the case study in Ukraine, transition towards a sustainable biogas energy system and organic agriculture on chernozem soils.

6.3.1. LMT Hub

Demand

The Ukrainian ecosystem

The Ukrainian ecosystem is of great importance to Europe²³: The system

- Covers 35 percent of Europe's biodiversity.
- Has more than 70 thousand biological species live here.
- Consists of 29% of the territory of Ukraine consists of natural vegetation and cultivated natural vegetation (for example, well-kept pastures and hedges).
- Has forests that make up 16% of the territory of Ukraine.
- Has almost 63,000 rivers flowing through Ukraine.
- Consists of 11% of the Carpathian Mountain massif and is located on the territory of Ukraine, where a third of all plant species in Europe grow.

Environmental issue

The level of harmful emissions exceeds the maximum permissible levels. Currently, emissions from thermal power plants in Ukraine exceed EU standards by 5–30 times. The conduct of hostilities deepens the climate

²³ [Scorched earth and polluted water: catastrophic environmental consequences of Russia's war against Ukraine](#)

crisis, causing significant emissions of carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. We have the most emissions²⁴:

- From hostilities - about 8.9 million tons of CO₂ eq
- From the movement of internally displaced persons - about 1 million tons of CO₂ eq
- From fires – more than 23.4 million tons of CO₂ eq
- Reclaim land damage from the war

Social issues

Ukraine's energy systems are under threat. Ukraine's "green" energy industry suffered considerable damage: 85% of wind and 50% of solar power plants were destroyed during the war. The country's centralised thermal power plants continue to be targeted without 50% of its energy infrastructure damaged by shelling²⁵.

The most polluted lands on the front line are the economic zone of Donbas, where the war has been going on since 2014. Even before the war, it was "loaded" from an ecological point of view. The content of harmful metals, such as copper, lead, cadmium, and chromium, consistently exceeds the norm by 3-4 times, and in some areas, the norm is exceeded by 25 times²⁶. Soil pollution will reduce the fertility of cultivated areas and affect people. Harmful substances from the soil will further enter the groundwater and directly into the crop, which will undoubtedly affect the health of consumers of such products.

Knowledge sources

The business case will use the following knowledge:

- Innovative knowledge through a local experience focused on using advanced technologies in collecting, storing, and transporting the agricultural waste, organic farming, and developing the gas transmission network.
- Local traditional knowledge: developed over a period of time through the accumulation of experience and a deep understanding of the environment. Local traditional knowledge about ecosystem management and using natural resources is one of the keys to combating climate change.
- Western scientific knowledge: this experience will include the experience, research, and practice of colleagues in Western countries/regions. Innovative knowledge is focused on using advanced technologies in collecting, storing, and transporting the agricultural waste, organic farming, and developing the gas transportation network.

Supply

Scaling up an independent energy system with a network of biogas plants and reproduction of soil fertility in organic farming. The ecological effect of biogas production consists of the environmentally safe processing of organic waste and by-products of animal origin due to methane fermentation.

²⁴ <https://eco.rayon.in.ua/news/563616-vnaslidok-viyini-v-ukraini-zafiksuvali-33-milyoni-tonn-vikidiv-v-atmosferu>

²⁵ [Information portal of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine](#)

²⁶ <https://naglyad.org/uk/2023/03/13/v-25-raziv-bilshe-shkidlivih-metaliv-u-gruntah-yak-vijna-zabrudnyuye-rodyuchi-chornozemi-ta-chi-mozhna-yih-vidnoviti/>

Resources

- Organic agricultural waste (waste from crop production, animal husbandry, and processing industries)
- Agrofood industry waste
- Land for biogas plants
- Organic fertilisers

The raw material for biogas production can be waste from plants and animals. But the most significant ecological effect is that biogas plants can solve the problem of manure disposal and droppings through fermentation. . At the output of such biogas installations, farmers have access to ecologically clean liquid or solid biofertilizers that do not contain unpleasant odours, helminth eggs, weed seeds, and nitrates.

Technologies/practices

1) This model requires technologies that

- Handle production waste
- Produce biogas, biomethane
- Produce organic fertilisers
- Store carbon in chernozem

The transformation of organic residues into biogas occurs due to the fermentation of biomass, which involves a range of complex biochemical changes.

2) Increasing and improving practices in organic production

6.3.2. Outputs

Market products

- Biogas, fertiliser, and food carbon credits for soil restoration, and organic farm outputs that can be sold at a price higher than conventional foods for European markets and beyond
- Reclaiming land damage from the war

Environment

- Higher air & soil quality
- Organic fertiliser reduces the impact of chemical fertilisers
- Improved other environmental qualities (e.g., water)
- Enhanced biodiversity
- Carbon market, CO₂ use/storage

The most significant ecological effect is that, as explained above, biogas plants can solve the problem of disposing of manure and droppings. They transform these organic residues into biogas through a fermentation process.

Society, community

This would have a number of additional benefits to society and the communities. These include:

- High quality of food
- Reduce waste of agro-production
- Farmers receive ecologically clean liquid or solid biofertilizers

- The energy supply of rural areas
- Rural population employment
- Livestock development
- Economic savings from use of biogas in communities

6.3.3. Other elements

Modelling

In the Ukraine business case, we can apply the DayCent model to investigate SOC sequestration I. The impact is to evaluate how the DayCent model represents changes in SOC and yield by comparing organic agriculture to conventional agriculture in the Chernozems. Then we will up-scale the potential of organic agriculture to (sub-)national scales, potentially using scenarios generated with the LANDSHIFT modelling, which explores changes in land use at the national scale.

The ALCES cumulative effect models will also be applied to simulate changes in landscape composition and show the responses to LMTs factors.

Carbon capture and carbon credits

Reducing emissions of CO₂ and other greenhouse gases by processing waste from the agro-food industry into biogas instead of traditional approaches and technologies for their storage and use.

Emissions reduction can be achieved by replacing energy produced from non-renewable sources with energy produced from biogas. Manure is stored in anaerobic ponds on many pig and cattle farms, resulting in methane emissions into the atmosphere. Reduction of methane emissions in biogas complexes will be achieved due to the capture of biogas followed by its burning in a cogeneration plant.

In addition, a reduction in emissions of another greenhouse gas - CO₂ - will be achieved since the production of electricity and thermal energy from renewable sources (biogas) will lead to the replacement of an equivalent amount of energy obtained as a result of burning fossil fuels at power plants that provide power to the power system.

Associated business opport-unities

Monitoring and consultancy can include:

- Waste management
- Biomass flow
- Production monitoring (monitoring of agrochemical quality incoming raw materials and outgoing organic fertilisers and quality control)
- Soil agrochemical and biochemical analysis
- Management of CO₂ emission in organic farming on chernozem soils (earth observations soil sampling)
 - Investigating SOC sequestration
 - Identify a portfolio of LMTs for Ukraine

Policies

- Streamlining of energy independence and food security strategies
- Policies supporting standardisation of monitoring and verifying carbon credits

7. Conclusions

Mitigation technologies based on best soil and land management practices provide solutions to the social and climate challenges facing rural areas. But these solutions are neither simple nor easy to implement structurally. They require land-use plans at the county level that put them at the centre of new social and economic models, with medium and long-term approaches, that take into account the benefits that ecosystem services bring to society. The success of these measures will depend on the capacity of these ecosystem services to generate wealth and new income for rural communities.

To successfully apply a LMT within a region, it is key to consider the local, traditional and/or Indigenous knowledge available. These people, as local inhabitants and primary users of the land, have a deep understanding of the opportunities and challenges of the region and, in the end, will be the people who will be most directly affected by the LMT. Consequently, the business case created around the LMT should deliver a series of environmental and relevant social co-benefits, including climate change mitigation, increased food security, improved water quality and availability, biodiversity conservation and promotion, and increased income and employment opportunities.

When undertaking such models, it is again essential to consider the knowledge of local populations. For decades, or centuries, good land management practices have been applied in a traditional way. At a time when innovation and responding to new challenges are converging in land use, this traditional knowledge gains value and offers solutions that, while traditional, are nonetheless highly innovative in our present context. It is necessary to take into account and invest in maintaining the wisdom of local populations so that this type of circular economy model based on mitigation can take root in the territories.

This traditional knowledge is vast and diverse, and by way of example only, can be synergistically combined with some fields of experience^{27 28} cited here as a basis for effective transfer:

- Agriculture and extensive livestock:
 - Promote sustainable management of agriculture and its integration into the landscape.
 - Improving access to climate information.
 - Cultivation of early or drought-resistant varieties.
 - Application of water and soil conservation techniques.
 - Practice of integrated soil fertility management.
 - Soil management for water and nutrient recirculation.
 - Development of water management master plans.
 - Development of water reservoirs on various scales.
 - Development of water sources and water points for grazing.
 - Delimitation and development of grazing areas. Holistic management.
 - Application of water-efficient irrigation techniques.

²⁷ https://ctaex.com/transfencia-tecnologica/ficheros/archivos/2021_09/mejores-practicas-manejo-shui-cereal-agua.pdf

²⁸ <https://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/246622>

- Forestry, agroforestry and nature conservation:
 - Land planning at a watershed scale.
 - Improved knowledge of biodiversity and its management for agro-ecosystem conservation.
 - Land management and agroforestry planning for better prevention of forest fires.
 - Application of good forestry and agroforestry practices (selective felling of firewood, assisted natural regeneration, controlled clearing, etc.).
 - Protection of watercourses and water sources.
 - Conservation and restoration of rivers and riverbanks.
 - Practice of agroforestry for sustainable management of natural resources.
 - Community and participatory management of forest, wildlife and fish resources.
- Energy:
 - Diversification of energy sources (solar, wind, biogas).
 - Promotion of energy-saving technologies in industry and the building industry.
 - Use of agriculture and/or forest waste for energy generation.

7.1. Drivers for land-based practices

The main driver for the implementation of new land-based practices is the demand identified in the LMT Hub scheme presented in this report. This demand, as mentioned before, is created by the society (needs of decision-makers, land use managers, farmers, etc.) as a response, mainly, to an environmental issue which in turn creates a business opportunity to fulfil this demand.

While carbon markets are the core focus for LANDMARC, carbon was not a driver for all case studies. Societal needs (i.e. a demand) plus carbon markets are a breakthrough in this regard, as they monetise environmental value and translate on-the-ground measurements of ecological variables, in this case, greenhouse gas emissions reduction and storage into monetary value. This market can lead the way for many other environmental benefits such as biodiversity, soil, air and water quality, which have not yet systematically found a way to economically benefit the agents and people that contribute to the improvement of these resources. Natural resources that are mainly part of the rural environment, which is also facing a depopulation crisis affecting large rural areas in Europe and other parts of the world. However, it is important to highlight that Burkina Faso is facing an increase in population, which is causing deforestation due to agriculture, grazing, and fuelwood collection; thus, agriculture productivity not only needs to be efficient, but soil quality also needs to improve to feed current and future generations. Carbon markets can be an important stimulant in these regions, to improve both soil nutrients and to invest in longer term sustainable agriculture practices.

Sustainable land-based mitigation practices are needed in many other case studies explored (eg. Spain, Portugal, Kenya, Nepal, Germany), as these areas must face environmental challenges such as low soil fertility, degraded agriculture and increased water scarcity. Carbon credits can also help to improve overall ecosystem services by helping to improve the overall quality of the soil and in turn improves resilience to climate change (e.g., drought). Other co-benefits include improved air quality and biodiversity. Carbon

credits can also be an important longer term financial mechanism to fund soil regeneration in Ukraine due to impacts from the war and promote food security and energy security

Consequently, in a context of climate change, it is important to come to sustainable solutions that encompass climate mitigation, as well as societal and environmental benefits. Building strong and diverse economic fabrics linked to rural territories and based on adaptation, mitigation, and nature conservation, together with other challenges that are not the subject of this deliverable, such as food security, is possible if social agents see good land use management practices as a source of wealth and societal and individual well-being. A source of wealth that must be converted into currency with a tangible and real value. This value needs to be adequately monitored and validated, creating further business opportunities. Finally, the environmental benefits include enhanced ecosystem adaptation and resilience, and ecosystem services.

7.2. Policies needed to promote LMTs

Special emphasis has been placed throughout the document on the need to develop and implement policies that lead to the maintenance of these land-use based mitigation technologies. Policies also need to be coordinated across policy areas, e.g., in rural development, forestry, agriculture, water, energy, and consider the entire supply and demand chain in the circular economy. We begin to explore the broader policy mixes in D2.5 “Guidance report for potential role of carbon-offsetting scheme and Paris Agreement”; but further research beyond this project is needed to consider the policy innovation along with the development of the LMT hub. Without the support of policies which send longer term signals to the market, there will be very limited investment in rural areas, and without this investment there will be no attraction of young and diverse talent to develop new life projects based on stable jobs and business models for the future. Business models can be based on a balance between innovation and tradition, science and technology, sustainability, and productivity. The LMT Hub system presented in this document can help develop such business models based on LMTs, as has been shown by the various case study applications presented.

In addition, policies need to be sufficiently flexible to account for local knowledge and avoid policy conflicts, for instance, the protection of natural areas may contradict the efforts needed to manage the land in a sustainable manner. Also, policies regulating the access to finance for farmers and managers are key, as the initial investment for the implementation of LMTs is often very high, limiting their application. This financial barrier can be partially addressed by carbon credits, but they require longer term business plans supported by policy incentives or grant schemes.

Thus, to support the implementation and scaling up of LMT, there needs to be dedicated efforts to explore policy mixes consisting of existing policies, and/or the policies in need of development, within the area of application. These policies can either act as enablers or limit the application of the LMT and the development of the business case. For more information about policy, see D5.4 “LMT Policy portfolios report”.

7.3. Final remarks

The LMT hub concept presented here is sufficiently flexible to be used in different sectors, accommodate circular feedback loops and co-benefits derived from the LMT implementation, and to adapt to the degree of the LMT implementation and to consider diverse stakeholders' knowledge.

This document has offered a conceptual and practical vision in different contexts and with different sectors, and present visions via the LMT hubs that aims to inspire policy and decision makers who want to improve the living conditions of rural societies.

Future work should aim at deepening the business cases outlined here and develop them further, including a financial assessment to determine their economic feasibility in the real world. This further work should include the development of more detailed revenue streams of LMTs, specifically considering the potential for carbon credits via different carbon monitoring tools. For carbon monitoring, future development of consultancy services that bridge science, technology and practice is key. However, land users are often resource poor in terms of time and finances and should not be expected to solve social problems. But researchers and consultants can bridge the gap between land-user manager's core activities and societal/environmental problems through the circularity concept of the LMT hub. These business cases then can actively include youth, women, and other populations in the hub design. Finally, the viability and sustainability of the business case in the long term will require the employment of land use models to assess different future scenarios for LMTs (considering a longer term of more than 10 years). This also includes considering the increasing value of carbon credits as we near the impending deadline to reduce emissions by 2030 and 2050. In this future scenario, the business case must also be strengthened with climatic risk reduction practices by improving the resilience of soil, and considering resource management (soil, water, and biodiversity) through research and better integrated management practices within the circular economy.

8. Appendix

8.1. Summary of earth observation system tools

Table A. Synthesis of CCMTs for CS application as presented in D3.8 (New Earth Systems Tools: Digital Agriculture and Forestry Tools)

		Platform	Type of information	LMT applications /usefulness	Carbon pool	Biodiversity	Spatial resolution (scale)	Revisit time	Collection effort	Cost (of data collection)	Specialised tools (for data collection)	Expert knowledge (for data collection)	Availability
<i>Remote sensing</i>	1.1. Drone data	Drone	Optical (4 bands)	Plant health, crop monitoring	Aboveground	Landscape diversity	8-15 cm/pixel	As needed	Medium	Medium	Yes	Yes	Local, ~50 ha/flight, anywhere
	1.2. a. LiDAR data (plane)	Plane	LiDAR	Forest monitoring, biomass	Aboveground	Landscape diversity	N/A	As needed (if hired)	Low	Variable (free in Spain, potentially very high elsewhere)	Yes	Yes	Local, potentially anywhere
	1.2. b. LiDAR data (GEDI)	International Space Station	LiDAR	Forest monitoring, biomass	Aboveground	Landscape diversity	N/A	Variable (higher frequency at -51.6 degrees N/S latitude, less in the equator)	Low	Free	No	No	Wide coverage, no observations above ~53 degrees N or below ~53 degrees S latitude)
	1.3. Sentinel-1	Satellite	Radar	Crop monitoring	Aboveground	Landscape diversity	N/A	12 days	Low	Free	No	No	Global coverage

		Platform	Type of information	LMT applications /usefulness	Carbon pool	Biodiversity	Spatial resolution (scale)	Revisit time	Collection effort	Cost (of data collection)	Specialised tools (for data collection)	Expert knowledge (for data collection)	Availability
	1.4. Sentinel-2	Satellite	Optical (13 bands)	Plant health, land cover, biomass, forest monitoring, water pollution, disaster mapping	Aboveground	Landscape diversity	10 m/pixel, 20 m/pixel, or 60 m/pixel depending on the band	5 days	Low	Free	No	No	Global coverage, limited by cloudy conditions
	1.5. Land Surface Temperature (MSG)	Satellite	Land surface temperature	Land surface temperature	Aboveground	No	3 km/pixel	15 minutes	Medium	Free	No	No	Wide coverage, limited by cloudy conditions
	1.6. Solar-Induced Fluorescence	Satellite	Solar induced fluorescence (SIF)	Plant growth/health	Above and belowground	No	5.5 km x 3.5 km/pixel	Less than 1 day	Low	Free	No	No	Global coverage, limited by cloudy conditions
Field data (in-situ)	2.1. Forest inventory (traditional + FieldMap)	Collection in the field	Aboveground biomass	Forest monitoring, biomass	Above (traditional + FieldMap) and belowground (traditional)	Plant species diversity	Point	As needed	High	High	Yes	No (but some training required)	Local, anywhere
	2.2. Eddy covariance	Collection in the field	Flux (carbon)	Carbon fluxes between the biosphere and the atmosphere	Above and belowground	No	Point, footprint depends on height of the tower and	As needed	Medium	High	Yes	Yes	Local, anywhere (limited)

		Platform	Type of information	LMT applications /usefulness	Carbon pool	Biodiversity	Spatial resolution (scale)	Revisit time	Collection effort	Cost (of data collection)	Specialised tools (for data collection)	Expert knowledge (for data collection)	Availability
							wind direction.						
	2.2. Soil sampling (physicochemical)	Collection in the field	Soil chemistry	Mineral carbon content	Belowground	No	Point	As needed	High	Medium	Yes	No (but some training required)	Local, anywhere
	2.2. Soil sampling (microbiological)	Collection in the field	Soil microbial genetics	Biological carbon content	Belowground	Microbiological diversity	Point	As needed	High	High	Yes	No (but some training required)	Local, anywhere

8.2. Description of the models

This appendix shows a short description of the models applied in LANDMARC. For more information, see D5.2 (Results from risk, co-benefit and trade-off assessment).

DayCent

Daycent is a *landuse biogeochemical ecosystem model* that can be applied for individual LMTs. DayCent can potential link information gather from in-situ Earth Observation tools to model the potential of a single LMT from the parcel level to the national level. DayCent will be applied to 10 number of case studies).

General description: DayCent is a daily-time step biogeochemical model of intermediate complexity that simulates ecosystem processes associated with carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) cycling, such as changes in soil organic matter, plant growth, nutrient availability and trace gas emissions in response to changes in climate, soil and land management.

In general, the capabilities of risk, co-benefits, and trade-off assessment with DayCent are limited to biogeochemical processes, such as reversibility of carbon sequestered in soil or biomass, climatic risks due to drought, changes in distribution of rainfall, and trade-off risks (e.g., yield). Risks and co-benefits that are not part of these processes, e.g., linked to availability of external inputs to soils, such as manure, need to be considered in scenario building or in setting the right boundary conditions. The same is true for co-benefits, e.g., it should be possible to reach a land equivalent ratio > 1 in agroforestry systems. The model also explores one LMT at one time thus does not explore trade-offs between different LMT applications.

We have used DayCent in the Swiss case study to illustrate the trade-off between higher soil carbon stocks and lower yields (about 30%) in organic agriculture. For reduced tillage, it seems that while the potential soil carbon sequestration is maximally half that of organic agriculture, there is not necessarily a trade-off with yield, which is expected to remain the same in reduced or no-till systems. This might provide some insights to stakeholder's concerns for impacts on yields and perceived trade-offs considering different techniques.

In the case of Kenya and ISFM, the first results of our national DayCent model application tells a somewhat different story. Our first results indicate that there is a co-benefit between higher soil carbon stocks with ISFM and higher yield.

Overall, most of the risks that stakeholders have mentioned seem to be of political, technical, financial, and social nature. As stated before, these may be important for setting the right boundary conditions for DayCent (e.g., in ISFM, we have, in accordance with stakeholder discussions, opted for a maximum yearly application of farmyard manure equivalent to 2t C per ha and year, only half of the high rates from the long-term experiment used in CS9). A direct consideration of such forces in biogeochemical models, such

as DayCent, is possible in coupled modelling frameworks that include agents-based models (e.g. (Marohn *et al.*, 2022). However, such a hard-coupling of different models is highly challenging and beyond the scope of LANDMARC.

ALCES

ALCES flow was specifically developed for LANDMARC case study leads with no prior modelling knowledge, and/or use in co-creation workshops with stakeholders. It is applied in 10 number of case study countries.

General description: ALCES flow is a land-use exploration model that uses stakeholder inputs to explore scenarios for the short to mid-term. It models land-use related LMTs with a novel approach for including stakeholder information and knowledge. The tool has been developed to provide a low barrier approach to co-creation of scenarios and land-use simulations with stakeholders. The model has the capacity to explore a portfolio of LMTs and thus is able to assess trade-offs between different LMT options.

Stakeholder inputs in ALCES flow are captured in a direct and indirect manner. First, their information can be used as inputs to directly inform the following:

- Carbon: More detailed information that stakeholders might have on the carbon effects that LMTs portfolios have on land-use.
 - § And subsequently provides information on the extent of stakeholder knowledge.
- Location: Where LMTs within an LMT portfolio are applied.
 - § And why the LMTs should be applied there.
- LMT applied: To what extent the LMT portfolio is applied.
 - § And why to this extent.

Indirectly, stakeholder information can provide context for designing the scenarios. These can be co-created on the spot with the stakeholders during a workshop and can also be based on the information that was captured in the surveys for this report. As such, the risks and co-benefits resulting from the interviews predominately provide the context for scenario explorations with the ALCES model. The risks and co-benefits related to implementation are interpreted as optimistic and pessimistic implementation of LMT portfolios, which can then be presented to stakeholders for further exploration.

As ALCES models for the short to mid-term (up to 2030), existing implementation risks and co-benefits can be directly interpreted as impacting optimistic and pessimistic implementation of that LMT. For example, risks that are unlikely to be mediated in the short term will likely have a strong impact on the implementation of that LMT in the short term. For instance, the lack of political, financial, or knowledge capacity to implement an LMT such as in agroforestry and wetlands is an example that would have an immediate impact on its upscaling in the short term. For LMTs with a short turnover time, such as organic agriculture, this could be a less ‘serious’ risk when compared to LMTs with a long turnover time, for instance agroforestry.

The risks that were mentioned by stakeholders which are related to lock-in of the land can be modeled in the choices that stakeholders make. This is reflected in ALCES through designing the LMT portfolio, and determining to what extent and where the portfolio is applied.

Another example are the risks and co-benefits related to infrastructure, and (lack of) access to resources in remote areas. These can direct where to apply the LMT portfolio, as well as provide understanding of why stakeholders apply the LMT to that extent in the area. A lack of infrastructure could lead to certain regions being ‘left behind’ for

Finally, trade-offs concerning land-use, for instance between carbon maximization and food production, are modeled by the ALCES model.

The ALCES model is a tool for land-use simulation and scenario exploration, strongly focused on co-creation with stakeholders. While some of the socio-economic, political, and technical risks are not directly modeled, they can be integrated through providing a contextual basis for scenario development. They also provide a knowledge basis for discussion and interactions with the stakeholders – exploring risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs with the stakeholders through a visual way in workshops.

LandSHIFT

LandSHIFT-N (national) is a *land system model* and its model result can be used as inputs to LandSHIFT-G (global) and EC-Earth Global atmosphere & carbon cycle model in WP7. LandSHIFT-N will be applied to 3 case studies at the national level.

General description: LandSHIFT is a spatially explicit model that simulates land use change dynamics and competition between different land-use activities (e.g., settlement, crop cultivation, livestock grazing, forestry) on grid level. Cell size varies between 250m for regional level applications and 5 arc-min in the global model version. Temporal resolution is between 1 and 5 years. The model downscales land-use drivers on the regional/country/local scale (e.g., demand for agricultural and forest products or LMT targets) to the grid cell level.

The LandSHIFT-N model simulates future land use and land cover of three case study countries resulting from changing demand for land of three competing categories of land use activities (crop production, livestock farming, and settlement). It uses a medium reference scenario (2020-2050) which prescribes area demand for settlement and agricultural production for food supply. As input information for the (additional) realization of LMT options, the model requires the quantity of area on which a portfolio of LMTs will be realized, in addition to a start date and a rate of realization. Information on the location or the most suitable areas for this activity is also required.

For example, the LandSHIFT-N model can take into account suitable areas for LMT implementation, such as degraded areas. These were mentioned in the context of stakeholder activities and can be implemented if spatial data is available. In addition, in cases where several LMTs compete for land (e.g. agroforestry and afforestation) a ranking/ prioritisation of LMTs is necessary.

In order to simulate LMT scenarios, the kind of information provided by stakeholder consultation cannot be implemented directly into the model since it focuses more on social, policy and financial aspects. However, the provided stakeholder insights are a valuable source to develop and enrich a limited number of scenario storylines. The co-benefits and risks, that are relevant for a country could, for instance, be translated into a scenario-specific set of measures and actions affecting the implementation and up-scaling of LMTs in a country. These actions together could, for example, either delay and/or hinder or promote the implementation of a particular LMT. This scenario-specific set of actions would need to be defined for each LMT option (e.g., agroforestry, paludiculture, etc.) and each scenario period (2020-2030 and 2030-2050). This information forms the backbone of the qualitative part of the scenario storylines, or scenario narratives.

To obtain the input for the LandSHIFT model, an additional step is necessary: qualitative pathways of LMT implementation have to be derived from the set of actions and measures, clearly distinguishing between the scenarios. For this purpose verbal expressions, such as “medium”, “slow” or “fast” could be used to describe the trend and pace of LMT development in a certain period of time. These terms can potentially be included in upcoming stakeholder workshops.

Subsequently, these qualitative trends have to be quantified in a meaningful, realistic and transparent way, e.g. by analysing historic trends or existing policy targets.

This approach has several challenges. First, clustering the information in a limited number of scenarios that are plausible, consistent and most of all useful for stakeholders: This requires a well moderated process. And it requires time. Second, an important consideration is to determine at which step should stakeholders be involved, and where cooperation between modellers and CS leads is more efficient.

E3ME

E3ME is a *global macroeconomic model* with national level components that can be used to assess the potential policy portfolios to support the scaling up of LMT portfolios. Results can also help to inform the scaling up of continental policy portfolios for the most promising LMTs in different continents. The model is applied 7 case study countries.

General description: E3ME is a global, macro-econometric model designed to address major economic and economy-environment policy challenges. The mode includes integrated treatment of the world's economies, energy systems, emissions and material demands. This enables it to capture two-way linkages and feedbacks between these components. It can fully assess both short and long-term impacts. The time resolution is annual but if larger intervals are required, E3ME can interpolate. The time horizon of the LMT implementation and the policy is an important part of scenario design. Stakeholder engagement can contribute to guiding future trajectories (e.g., political and technological feasibility). E3ME currently solves to 2050.

E3ME is a macro-econometric model that integrates the world's economic and energy systems and the environment. It is primarily used for scenario analysis (i.e., difference from an established baseline) and can capture both overall macroeconomic impacts on jobs and economy, but also sectoral impacts. The model can consider LMT portfolios and their potential corresponding policies.

For the most part, there is no endogenous model treatment in E3ME of the technical details of different LMTs, nor of the impacts of LMT policies on LMT activities. When modelling LMT scenarios in E3ME, the scale of the LMT activity itself and the associated techno-economic factors (e.g. CAPEX and OPEX costs, CO2 emissions, etc.) are usually entered into the model by assumption. Thus stakeholder knowledge could potentially be in terms of their assumed outcome.

It is therefore important that these assumptions about potential LMTs incorporate a reasonable external assessment of costs, risks and co-benefits internal to the activity itself. This assessment could potentially be a useful contribution from the stakeholder engagement tasks to our modelling. For example:

- In the Canada case study, we modelled a scenario featuring restoration of peatland which had been degraded through oil extraction activity. A detailed set of input assumptions were required regarding the extent of peatland restoration, land management costs, potential carbon removals, and the quantity of oil production affected. It is important that these assumptions regarding the scale and costs of the LMT activity are realistic.
- In the Germany case study, we assumed an increase in forestry production. The E3ME modelling does not assess the feasibility of the scale of this increase, so the assumptions need to incorporate reasonable assessments of risks and opportunities.
- In the Netherlands case study, we assumed the development of new biogas with CCS plants. We effectively assumed that there are sufficient people with the necessary skills in place to build and run these plants, although this is a potential risk in scaling up this technology. We also assumed that captured carbon was sold to other sectors, an opportunity that would otherwise have been missed in the endogenous model dynamics.
- In the Sweden case study, for lack of good data on which to base an assumption, we have not assumed any cost reduction from economies of scale in the rollout of biochar. This diffusion effect is a potential opportunity that is not captured in our modelling.

Once these technoeconomic assumptions are made, the added value of the E3ME model is then to estimate the impacts of the LMT activities on the macroeconomic and energy systems. E3ME is well-suited to capturing risks, trade-offs and co-benefits, to the extent that they exist within these macroeconomic and energy systems. For example:

- In Canada case study mentioned above, there is a clear trade-off between the health of the peatland, and the economic potential of the oil sector. Once the work of developing technoeconomic assumptions is in place, the E3ME modelling was able to assess the ultimate macroeconomic trade-offs between the lost oil activity, the additional employment from peatland management, and the revenues from carbon credits.
- In the Sweden case study, we modelled the impacts of carbon credits paid by the government for carbon removals from biochar and BECCS. However, in a scenario with a balanced budget, paying for these credits required raising tax rates for tax payers. This therefore creates a trade-off between the revenues received by the carbon-removing industry, and the cost to Swedish citizens from a higher tax burden.
- In the Germany case study, the increase in forestry output leads to co-benefits for the supply chain of the forestry sector, including for example the machinery required for management of forests.
- In the Netherlands case study, attention was paid to how peatland drainage can lead to soil subsidence and structural damage to property. Restoration of peatlands would therefore have the co-benefit of allowing costs from this damage to be avoided. However, even in the base case where the property is damaged, there is a compensatory benefit from the additional investment and employment required to maintain and repair the buildings. So the costs of the damage to the

buildings (i.e. the stock of the nation's fixed assets) can be effectively traded off against the lost employment in the construction industry (i.e. the flow of national income).

In addition to the technoeconomic assumptions, there are potential *second-order* risks, opportunities, co-benefits and trade-offs of LMT activities that are not covered by the E3ME model. Again, these can be modelled by assumption, although in many cases the expected impacts are negligible (especially when modelling at a national level), so consideration needs to be given as to whether the time invested in developing assumptions is worthwhile. These second-order dynamics include (but are not limited to):

- Impacts of climate change (which may be marginally impacted by negative emissions from LMT activities) on economic output and productivity.
- Impacts of the LMT activity on biodiversity, and corresponding feedbacks to economic output and productivity.
- Health co-benefits from cleaner air.